

NERSC

MPI

European Commission Environment and Climate Programme 1994-98-Topic 1.1.1

Acoustic monitoring of the Ocean Climate in the Arctic Ocean

AMOC

Task 4

Concept study of acoustic monitoring of temperature and current changes in the Fram Strait

**Project coordinator: Ola M. Johannessen,
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center,
Edv. Griegsvei 3a,
N-5059 Bergen
Norway**

SPRI

Authors:

**Halvor Hobæk, Ola M. Johannessen, Hanne Sagen,
Konstantin A. Naugolnykh, Igor B. Esipov and Elena Evert**

Contract Number: ENV4-CT97-0463

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Edv. Griegsvei 3a,
N-5059 Bergen

NORWAY.

Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50

e-mail: administrasjonen@nrsc.no

Internet: <http://www.nrsc.no/>

*a non-profit environmental research
center affiliated with the university of
Bergen*

NERSC Technical Report

<p>TITLE</p> <p>AMOC Task 4 Concept study of acoustic monitoring of temperature and current changes in the Fram Strait</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION</p> <p>NERSC Technical Report no. 196</p>
<p>CLIENT</p> <p>European Commission Environment and Climate Programme 1994-1998. Topic 1.1.1</p>	<p>CONTRACT</p> <p>ENV4-CT97-0463</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE</p> <p>Claus Bruning</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY</p> <p>Open</p>
<p>PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS</p> <p>Ola M. Johannessen Klaus Hasselmann Peter Wadhams Leonid Bobylev</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION</p> <p>Bergen, January 2001</p> <p>DIRECTOR</p> <p>Ola M. Johannessen</p>
<p>AMOC partners:</p> <p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Hamburg, Germany Scott Polar Research Institute, United Kingdom Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Russia</p>	

Executive Summary

Subtask 4.1 Topographical influence on the acoustic insonification of the Fram Strait for optimal receiver and source configuration.

Calculations have been carried out using OASES, RAM and RAY models for the track along 79°N in the Fram Strait. The conclusions are as follows:

- For the source at the shallow shelf location the best signal to noise ratio is obtained when the source is positioned at 122m depth.
- The sources/receivers positions should be off the shelf in order to avoid that the deeper going part of the acoustic field is influenced by bathymetry.
- Deep source gives a better insonification of the water masses for high frequencies.
- Calculation of the transmission loss as a function of the depth and range at high frequency can be use for monitoring oceanographic changes.
- Sedimentation significantly influence on acoustic propagation when the source is located at the shallow shelf.
- With respect to a good enough signal to noise ratio for low frequency receivers should be positioned in the upper 1000m of the ocean while for high frequencies in the upper 500m.

Subtask 4.2 Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes

Calculations have been carried out using OASES, RAM and RAY models for the track along 79°N in the Fram Strait. The sound speed input is from the US-Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean, and bathymetry from TerrainBase. The conclusions are as follows:

For a shallow source (60m):

- The seasonal variations (implying temperature and salinity variations) are clearly observed at all selected receiver depths (60, 122, 250 and 500m).
- Less variations seen for the lowest receiver (at 500m depth).
- Summer conditions are more stable than the winter conditions.

For a deep source (500m):

- Some seasonal variation seen for the shallow receivers (at 60 and 122m depths).
- More stable situation with respect to seasonal changes is observed for the deep receiver locations (at 250 and 500m depths).
- Travel time variations can be used for monitoring temperature and general structure changes.

A study of the stability of rays in the Eastern part of the Fram Strait with respect to seasonal environmental variations and passages of meso scale eddies, concludes as follows.

- Although there are large changes during passing seasons and eddies, some of the rays show a remarkable stability, and ought to be recognizable in an experimental situation for more than 50 % of the time. Furthermore, these rays are the deepest going rays, typically down to 0.8 - 1 km, and accordingly map the most important part of the West Spitsbergen

current.

- In an experimental situation it is advisable to use a vertical receiving array, with receivers covering depths between 200 - 700 m, perhaps arranged in pairs so that the direction of received rays can be established at different depths.

The arrival time fluctuations were investigated for changing oceanographic data. Environmental data variation was provided by shifting the entire sound-speed pattern horizontally with respect to the transmitter-bottom-receiver configuration for a distance essentially more the scale of ocean turbulence spatial correlation. For the isotropic ocean turbulence in each horizontal plane, when the spatial scale of correlation of random oceanographic inhomogeneities is the same in any direction in the horizontal plane, we obtain the rms travel time fluctuations for the 5s arrival close to 30 ms. This value is noticeably larger than signal fluctuations due to surface scattering and ice cover influence. The temperature influence on the stable arrivals was estimated as a gradient of 29 ms/°C for 4s arrival and 37 ms/°C for 5s arrival.

Two approaches are considered in the modeling. One of them is based on the stable arrivals selection and determination of travel time variation. The second one consists of defining the trend in the whole signal-arrival spectrum caused by the temperature changes, and computing average parameters of the arriving signal ensemble.

In the course of implementing the second approach there were obtained the collective sum of signal arrivals. The temperature dependence of the arrival-pattern duration leads to variation of the slope of the cumulative sum regression line. The advantage of this approach is that it is based only on relative measurements of arrivals. Measurement of the regression line slope does not require as sophisticated an apparatus to match the receiver and the source clock as it required for travel time measurements. The cumulative time procedure presents the possibility of determining the average temperature along the acoustic path in the ocean without considering detail arrival features. Statistical approach applied for travel time calculation for the signal propagated across the Fram Strait through the decades reveals some trends, which could be related with temperature change in upper layer of the ocean mostly in winter environment conditions. The following conclusion was obtained.

- Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes. Cumulative sum (CUMSUM) and Collective Arrivals Time (CAT) as statistical methods have been considered to find the temperature dependence on acoustical propagation in cross section of Fram Strait. CUMSUM method is sensitive to the temperature variation in depth (baroclinic dependence), whereas CAT changes mostly at barotropic temperature effect. 0.1°C per a year or 0.06°C per a decade sensitivity can be reached under the permanent seasonal acoustical monitoring of temperature in Fram Strait.

A separate study using data from the climatic simulations in Task 2 as input to ray tracing model (RAY), for comparison with similar simulations using measured environmental data led to the following conclusions:

- Comparison of ray travel times simulated with climatic models and measured mean environmental data show a very good correspondence.
- For the sound tracks used in this study the climatic simulations indicate an expected decrease in travel time of 6 ms/year.

- The measured environmental data for the period 1950-1989 show no systematic change in the mean water temperature in the Fram Strait.

Subtask 4.3 Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to current velocity changes

Space-time scintillation analysis offers a promising method of remote acoustic sensing of current in the ocean. The evolution of the scintillation pattern is related to the advection of the inhomogeneous medium through the sound beam, thus providing a basis for flow velocity measurement. A sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to current velocity changes resulted in the following conclusions.

- Signal scintillation approach was developed to retrieve current profile in Fram Strait cross section in small aperture tomography scheme. Both CAT and Stable Ray approaches have been considered for application of signal scintillation procedure. 10% accuracy can be in inversion procedure for 4'4 array of 15 km aperture for 210 km path. Double frequency signal scintillation method was considered to transverse advection velocity detect. This method can be regarded as a "frequency-domain" version of the scintillation approach based on the measurement of correlation of the signals transmitted from the source to two separated in space receivers and can be developed to realize 'one path tomography scheme'.
- Preliminary estimations of bottom autonomous system has been done for the small aperture tomography scheme in Fram Strait cross section.

Table of contents

1. Objective and subtasks.....	1
2. Outline of the geophysical environmental characteristics of the Fram Strait.....	2
2.1 Introduction.....	2
2.1.1 Oceanography of the Arctic Ocean and the Fram Strait.....	2
2.1.2 Ice conditions in the Fram Strait.....	3
2.1.3 Tidal currents.....	3
2.1.4 Internal Waves.....	3
2.2 The acoustical environment of the Fram Strait.....	3
2.2.1 Sources of environmental data.....	5
2.2.2 Averaged environmental data.....	5
2.2.3 Meso scale eddy data sets.....	8
2.2.4 Meso scale eddy simulation.....	9
2.2.5 Ambient noise in the Fram Strait.....	10
2.3 Acoustical simulation models.....	13
2.4 References.....	13
3. Topographical influence on the acoustic insonification of the Fram Strait for optimal receiver and source configuration (Subtask 4.1).....	15
3.1 Study the influence of the smooth bottom on acoustic propagation in the Fram Strait.....	15
3.2 Reflection loss.....	16
4. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes (Subtask 4.2).....	25
5. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes using the cumulative sum and collective arrival time approach (Subtask 4.2).....	32
5.1 Introduction.....	32
5.2 Oceanographic model.....	33
5.3 Travel time variation.....	34
5.4 Cumulative signal storage.....	37
5.5 Collective arrivals time change.....	39
5.6 Conclusion.....	41
5.7 References.....	41
5.8 Deliverables/Publications.....	43
6. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to current velocity changes using signal scintillation approaches (Subtask 4.3).....	44
6.1 Introduction.....	44
6.2 Computer modeling of the 3D environment.....	44
6.3 Signal scintillation approach.....	46
6.4 Multi-frequency scintillation method for transverse ocean current measurement.....	50
6.5 Summary and discussion.....	53
6.6 Conclusion.....	55
6.7 References.....	55

6.8	Deliverables/Publications	55
7.	Stability of individual rays in the Fram Strait	56
7.1	Abstract.....	56
7.2	Introduction.....	56
7.3	Method.....	56
7.3.1	Eigenrays	58
7.3.2	Ray fans	58
7.4	Results.....	58
7.4.1	Seasonal data-eigenrays	58
7.4.2	Meso data -eigenrays	61
7.4.3	Seasonal data -ray fans.....	62
7.4.4	Meso data - ray fans	62
7.5	Discussion.....	63
7.5.1	Seasonal variations.....	63
7.5.2	Meso scale eddy variations	64
7.5.3	Thermometry.....	65
7.6	Conclusion	65
7.7	References.....	65
7.8	Source code.....	66
8.	Comparison of ray fans simulated with decadal mean environmental data and data from clima simulations under Task 2	91
8.1	Conclusions.....	91
9.	Acknowledgement	93

Table of figures

Figure 2.1 Sound speed profile along 79° N for the mean of summers 1950 through 1980s. Left: raw ssp-profiles, offset by 3 m/s for each station from Greenland side towards Svalbard (sound speed axis is correct only for the first (leftmost) profile). Right: Colormap of the same interpolated and with bathymetry added.	6
Figure 2.2 As Figure 2.1 for the mean of winters 1950 through 1980s.....	6
Figure 2.3 Difference in sound speed between decades, at the deepest profile (293 km). Left: Summers 50 to 80. Right: Winters 50 to 80..	7
Figure 2.4 Difference in sound speed between seasons in the same decade, at the deepest profile (293 km).....	7
Figure 2.5 Sound speed profiles showing meso scale activity - from the AOGC97 expedition September 97. Left: SEASOAR data, taken on 14/09. Right: CTD-data taken on 16/09.	9
Figure 2.6 POLARSTERN sound speed profile data showing meso scale activity, taken in March 1993.....	9
Figure 2.7 Plot of averaged ambient noise level observed on April 30, 1985 at 122 m depth as a function of least distance from the ice edge.	11
Figure 2.8 Plot of averaged ambient noise level at 122 m, obtained on April 2, 1987, according to least distance from the ice edge.	12
Figure 2.9. Observed noise level versus frequency in the Fram Strait.	12
Figure 3.1 Sound speed fields derived from oceanographic data included on the Joint US-Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean for means summer (upper) and winter (lower) conditions 1980s across the Fram Strait long 79°N.....	18
Figure 3.3 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =20Hz.....	20
Figure 3.4 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =100Hz.....	20
Figure 3.5 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 60m. Frequency =100Hz.....	21
Figure 3.6 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 60m. Frequency =500Hz.....	21
Figure 3.7 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 500m. Frequency =500Hz.....	22
Figure 3.8 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean summer conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =20Hz.....	23
Figure 3.9 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean summer conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =100Hz.....	23
Figure 3.10 Reflection loss as a function of grazing angle and frequency calculated by OASES for varying sediment layer thickness.	24
Figure 4.1 Plot of the eigenrays found at 240 km from the source. Means winter 1950s conditions. Source depth = Receiver depth = 60m (upper). Source depth = Receiver depth = 500m (lower).	26
Figure 4.2 Plot of the eigenrays found at 240 km from the source. Means summer 1950s conditions. Source depth = Receiver depth = 60m (upper). Source depth = Receiver depth = 500m (lower).	27
Figure 4.3 Arrival times for eigenrays found at 240km from the source vs selected receiver depths (60, 122, 250 and 500m) (mean 1950s-1980s); blue '*' - winter, red 'o' - summer; Source depths=60m(a); =122m(b); =250m(c); =500m(d).	28
Figure 4.4 Averaged sound speed along eigenrays found at 240 km from the source positioned 60m below the sea surface for winter (blue) and summer (red) averaged conditions for each decades (1950s, 1960s, 1970s, 1980s). Receiver depth = 60m (upper) and 500m (lower).....	29
Figure 4.5 Averaged sound speed along eigenrays found at 240 km from the source positioned 500m below the sea surface for winter (blue) and summer (red) averaged conditions for each decades (1950s, 1960s, 1970s, 1980s). Receiver depth = 60m (upper) and 500m (lower).....	30
Figure 5.1 Fram Strait acoustical path.....	34
Figure 5.2 Sound speed profile in Fram Strait (March, 1993).	34
Figure 5.3 Stable configuration of 4s and 5s rays along the path.	35
Figure 5.4 Travel time variation as a function of temperature change for 4s and 5s arrivals. Curves 1, 2 and 3 correspond to receiver depth 100m, 200m, and 300m.	36
Figure 5.5 Cumulative sum regression lines versus signal arrival times for different subsurface layer temperature. Labels indicate the subsurface layer temperature increase ΔT and oceanographic pattern shift in km. Label (0°C, 0 km) corresponds to initial environmental realization, (0°C, 30 km) to that shifted at 30 km.	38
Figure 5.6 Regression line slope a as a function of water temperature. Solid line shows a linear approximation $a(\Delta T)$ dependence.....	38
Figure 5.7 Travel time variation cross the Fram Strait through the decades from 50s to 80s years. a) – time propagation change along the ray	

stable through the decades and seasons; b) – collective arrivals time change in seconds; c) – cumulative sum change in seconds. Shadowed areas show the values calculated for interpolated data, solid lines correspond to least square regressions.....	40
Figure 6.1 Spatial spectra (or periodograms) of the simulated sound speed variations. Curves 2,3,4,5 corresponds 40h, 280 h , 560 h and 700 h time delay for the environment velocity drift $u = 0.9 \text{ km/h}$	46
Figure 6.2 Two adjacent sets of signal arrivals separated of 20 min of environment shift (a,b), ordinates show the value of signal dampening with respect to the level at 1 km distance from the source; c - appropriate cross-correlation function for normalized arrivals shown at (a,b).....	47
Figure 6.3 Travel time variation of the signal crossed the simulated moving environment.....	48
Figure 6.4 Scheme of tomography array.....	48
Figure 6.5 Example of water current retrieval. Solid line shows the initial current profile, shadowed areas show the relative value of array tuning in accord with the rule put at the Table 6.1.	49
Figure 6.6 The coherence function of log-amplitude fluctuations of CW signal, with the different frequency separation Ω , propagating through the media perturbed by internal waves with Gurret-Munk spatial power spectrum ($\epsilon=0.04, p=1.7$).....	52
Figure 7.1 Bathymetry of the Fram Strait and mean sound speed distribution in the summers 1950s. The position of sound source and receiver used in the ray tracing is also indicated.....	57
Figure 7.2 (a) Transmission loss by RAM simulation. Source depth 100 m, frequency 100 Hz. (b) Transmission loss by RAM simulation. Source depth 500 m, frequency 100 Hz.....	57
Figure 7.3 (a) Sound speed distribution in the Fram Strait summer 70s. Original environmental data. (b) Sound speed distribution in the Fram Strait summer 70s. Meso data inserted at 300 km.....	71
Figure 7.4 (a) Eigenrays for the case shown in Figure 7.3(a). (b) Eigenrays for the case shown in Figure 7.3(b).....	72
Figure 7.5 Ray arrivals for factor=0.....	73
Figure 7.6 Ray arrivals for factor=0.2.....	73
Figure 7.7 Ray arrivals for factor=0.5.....	74
Figure 7.8 Ray arrivals for factor=1.0.....	74
Figure 7.9 Ray A variation with meso data.....	75
Figure 7.10 Ray B variation with meso data.....	75
Figure 7.11 Ray I variation with meso data.....	76
Figure 7.12 Arrival time for the identified rays versus amplitude of meso data.....	76
Figure 7.13 Ray fan results for Summer 50s.(a) Depth vs. source angle.(b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	77
Figure 7.14 Ray fan results for Winter 50s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	78
Figure 7.15 Ray fan results for summer 60s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	79
Figure 7.16 Ray fan results for Winter 60s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	80
Figure 7.17 Ray fan results for Summer 70s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	81
Figure 7.18 Ray fan results for Winter 70s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	82
Figure 7.19 Ray fan results for Summer 80s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	83
Figure 7.20 Ray fan results for Winter 80s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	84
Figure 7.21 Ray fan results for Summer 50s. (a) Depth vs. receive angle. (b) Receive angle vs. source angle. (c) Arrival time vs. receive angle.....	85
Figure 7.22 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with no range dependence - i.e. ssp as at the source. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	86
Figure 7.23 (a) Trace of rays belonging to region "ST". (b) Trace of rays of type a, A, g and h for all seasons.....	87
Figure 7.24 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with meso-scale eddy at amplitude 0.2, 10% margins, insertion point 300 km. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	88
Figure 7.25 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with meso-scale eddy at amplitude 1.0, 10% margins, insertion point 300 km. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.....	89
Figure 7.26 Arrival time of eigenrays a, A, g, and h through seasons and decades. The winter seasons are shifted one year with respect to the summer seasons, and 109 s must be added to the ordinate.....	90
Figure 8.1 Travel time from Task 2 climate simulations.....	92
Figure 8.2 Travel time from environmental data.....	92

1. Objective and subtasks

Simulation of present and future acoustic propagation in the Fram Strait to investigate the sensitivity of acoustic methods for monitoring heat and volume fluxes in an area of strong mesoscale eddy activity.

Task 4 consists of the following subtasks:

Subtask 4.1. Topographical influence on the acoustic insonification of the Fram strait for optimal receiver and source configuration.

Subtask 4.2. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes.

Subtask 4.3. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to current velocity changes.

Two institutions are involved in this task: NERSC and NIERSC. Task leaders are K.A. Naugol'nykh, NIERSC (Task 4.2, 4.3) and H. Sagen, NERSC (Task 4.1)

The report is organized as follows. Chapter 2 describes the general geophysical environment of the Fram Strait, the acoustical environment, the data sets used in this report and the acoustic models used for simulations. Chapter 3 and 4 describe results regarding subtask 4.1 and 4.2, performed at NIERSC. Chapter 5 and 6 describe results regarding subtask 4.2 and 4.3 performed by subcontractor. Chapter 7 is a separate study performed at NERSC, of ray stability during changing environmental conditions in the Fram Strait, which is relevant to acoustical thermometry.

2. Outline of the geophysical environmental characteristics of the Fram Strait

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by NERSC personnel.

2.1 Introduction

The Fram Strait is the sound between Greenland and Svalbard and is the main area for exchange of water masses, heat flux and sea ice between the Arctic Ocean and the Greenland Sea and the Norwegian Sea. About 240 km of the 600 km wide Fram Strait at 79° N is more than 2000 m deep. The maximum sill depth between the Greenland Sea and the Arctic Ocean is 2600 m, allowing deep-water masses to be exchanged through the Fram Strait. A 300 km wide continental shelf of less than 400 m depth covers the Greenland side of the strait. On the Svalbard side the shelf is less than 100 km wide. The bathymetry of the Fram Strait along the 79° N latitude is seen in Figure 2.1. The width of the Fram Strait allows inflow of warm water to the Arctic Ocean and outflow of cold water and ice to be separated horizontally, with the warm water flowing northwards on the Svalbard side. The Greenland side of the Fram Strait is ice covered all year round, dominated by multi year ice.

2.1.1 Oceanography of the Arctic Ocean and the Fram Strait

The water mass structure of the Arctic Ocean and adjacent seas is characterized by relatively cold and low salinity waters in the surface layer which are determined by seasonal variability of the ice cover (melting and freezing) and outflow of fresh water from rivers. Warmer and more saline waters are found at intermediate depths originating from inflow of Atlantic water. The deep-water masses, which occupy most of the water column, are quite homogeneous with variability in temperature of order 0.1°C and in salinity of order 0.02 ‰. The temperature structure in the upper few hundred meters defines a very strong vertical gradient in the sound speed profiles at a depth between 80 and 150 m; this gradient defines the lower boundary of the characteristic surface duct in the Arctic Ocean.

The current system in the Fram Strait is dominated by the shallow southward flowing cold and low salinity East Greenland Current (EGC) which exports ice and polar water out of the Arctic Ocean, and the northward flowing warm and saline Atlantic water in the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC). The WSC is a continuation of the Norwegian North Atlantic current, which branches northwards (WSC) and eastwards (North Cape Current) off the northern coast of Norway. The polar front separates the warm Atlantic water from the cold Arctic water. The Arctic water is close to freezing point and dominates the upper part of the water column north of the polar front.

The currents in the Fram Strait (and Barents Sea) are characterized by high mesoscale variability, which has strong influence on the ice configuration as well as on acoustic sound propagation. The Marginal Ice Zone (MIZ) is in general associated with ocean fronts observed as horizontal gradients in salinity, temperature and density. The fronts separate lighter, colder and less saline water beneath the ice cover from heavier, warmer and more saline water outside the MIZ. Mesoscale features along the ice edge region represent an important mechanism to exchange and mix water masses across the fronts.

Many of the mesoscale eddies propagate through the Fram Strait as part of the general circulation in the area. There are also stationary eddies locked to topographic features (such as the Molloy Deep). Mesoscale eddies, vortex pairs and ice tongues have characteristic horizontal

scales from 10 to 50 km, and life time from a few days to a few weeks (Johannessen, O. M., et al. 1987; Johannessen, J. A. et al., 1987). The Fram Strait and Greenland Sea eddies are often cyclonic with orbital speeds up to 40 cm/s. The velocity field in eddies and vortex pairs is characterized by strong horizontal shear observed in the ice floe pattern and by drifting buoys.

2.1.2 Ice conditions in the Fram Strait

The western part of the Fram Strait is ice covered almost all year around. The ice cover consists mainly of broken-up multiyear and first-year floes, which are transported southwards with the East Greenland Current. The interior part is dominated by large floes of first-year and multiyear ice and leads which can be open or covered by thin ice. The multiyear floe size is generally much larger than for first-year ice. In convergence zones ridges are formed which may be more than 5 m above sea level and corresponding ice keels can extend several tens of meters below sea level.

2.1.3 Tidal currents

Tidal currents consist of many constituents where the most important in the Fram Strait and Barents Sea are the semidiurnal M_2 and S_2 and diurnal K_1 and O_1 constituents (Kowalik and Proshutinsky 1994). The diurnal components can be trapped due to non-uniform bottom topography as found at the shelf break where the tidal current can be enhanced. Maximum tidal current speeds, which range from 50 to 130 cm/s, are found on the continental shelf of Svalbard, especially on the Spitzbergen Bank in the Barents Sea. A considerable velocity shear, between $50 - 100 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is found in all ice covered regions on the shelves surrounding the Arctic Ocean, including the area south of Svalbard. A high shear (above 10^{-6}) favors the generation of leads and regions of high internal ice stress. The interaction between tidal current and the ice cover causes strong periodic fluctuations in low frequency ambient noise, where maximum ambient noise coincide with maximum tidal velocity (Johannessen et al. 1992; Bourke and Parsons 1993).

2.1.4 Internal Waves

High-frequency internal waves can occur anywhere in the ocean where there is vertical stratification and generating mechanisms. Studies in ice covered regions show that internal waves can be generated by several mechanisms such as current interaction with seamounts, ice keels moving relative to the underlying water masses, and interaction with eddies and current shear (Sandven and Johannessen, 1987). Internal waves can be manifested by SAR observations at the surface and underwater arrays of temperature profiles. Investigations of internal waves in the Fram Strait MIZ show that density and corresponding temperature surfaces in the pycnocline can oscillate vertically with amplitudes up to 5 m and a frequency of typical 3 - 4 cycles per hour, which is near the buoyancy frequency for internal waves. These oscillations will have impact on the sound velocity profiles and the acoustic propagation conditions (Dyer et al., 1987, Lynch et al., 1996) as well as on low frequency ambient noise (Makris and Dyer, 1991).

2.2 The acoustical environment of the Fram Strait

The conditions for propagation of sound waves in the Fram Strait is governed by

- 1) Sound speed profile (SSP)
- 2) Bathymetry

- 3) Surface reflections (waves, ice cover)
- 4) Noise conditions

To some extent also steady currents influence on sound propagation. Meso scale eddy activity, internal and tidal waves all interact with sound propagation particularly through perturbations of the sound speed profile.

Several expeditions have studied the sound propagation in the Fram Strait and the neighboring waters during later years. **Table 2.1** summarizes some highlights of acoustic propagation studies in these waters since mid 1980-s. These investigations generally used source frequency at a few hundred Hz, except in the Marginal Ice Zone Experiment (MISEX 84) propagation study and in the numerical study by Mellberg et al. (1987). During MIZEX 84 acoustic waves were transmitted over a 100 km path, in order to study Doppler shifts and fluctuations in the same, due to quasi-steady motion of source and receiver caused by dynamic processes, such as internal waves and ice edge eddies in the marginal ice zone (Dyer et al. 1987). Another major acoustic study in the neighboring waters of the Fram Strait was the yearlong tomography experiment in the Greenland Sea in 1988-1989 (Worcester et al. 1993). This experiment consisted of six 250 Hz acoustic transceivers arranged in a pentagon with a sixth in the center. Inversion of averaged acoustic travel times gave range averaged potential temperature along the source-receiver paths (Worcester et al. 1993). Results showed that tomographic inversions were largely consistent with hydrological data samples collected during the recordings. This experiment also show that the acoustic travel times and amplitudes are sensitive to the depth of the surface duct and to the elastic parameters of the ice cover, of which the shear wave speed and the thickness are the most important ones (Jin et al. 1993).

Table 2.1 Some recent acoustic propagation studies in the Fram Strait.

References	Geographical location – Study objective – Data used - Main results
Dyer et al. 1987	Greenland Sea, 80°N (MISEX 84). Doppler shift and fluctuations in these due to eddies and other mesoscale motions. Path lengths (partly ice covered) 100 km, frequencies 20 Hz to 200 Hz.
Mellberg et al. 1987	Numerical study of sound propagation (not accounting for ice-cover and bottom reflection) using oceanographic data from MISEX 84 as input to a ray model and a PE-model. Result: eddies may refract sound and cause transmission loss fluctuations up to 20 dB. In particular it was found that at 1 kHz the loss could be more than 20 dB smaller than at 50 Hz!
Lynch et al. 1987	North of Svalbard (MIZEX 1984). Feasibility studies of acoustical tomography, using two receivers (one stationary and one drifting with ice) at 224 Hz. Results were generally positive.
Sutton et al. 1993	The Greenland Sea Tomography Experiment 1988-1989. Six transceivers in a pentagon configuration with a sixth instrument at the center. Source depth 100 m, frequency 250 Hz with a bandwidth of 120 Hz. Effects of seasonal changes in surface duct characteristics on travel time were studied, using ray theory and mode theory. It was found that a delay of the acoustic energy cut-off with several hundred milliseconds in intermediate profiles (very shallow ducts) compared to summer and winter profiles.
Jin et al. 1993	The Greenland Sea Tomography Experiment 1988-1989. Investigations of the effects of sea ice on acoustic ray travel times. Results show that ice thickness and shear speed are the most important ice parameters influencing the travel time.
Worcester et al. 1993	The Greenland Sea Tomography Experiment 1988-1989. Study of the evolution of the large-scale temperature field, focusing on inversions of averaged travel times in order to obtain range averaged potential temperature along source-receiver pairs. Results showed that tomographic inversions were largely consistent with fragmented hydrological data collected during the recordings.

2.2.1 Sources of environmental data

In the present study acoustic environmental data from 5 different sources have been used:

1. Arctic Oceanography Atlas CDs, 1997. Processed under Task 1 to yield decadal means of summer and winter stations for the period 1950 – 1989.
2. AOGC97 – ctd-data of meso scale eddy along 79°N September 1997
3. AOGC97 – SEASOR data of meso scale eddy along 79°N September 1997
4. Polarstern data of meso scale eddy along 79°N 1993
5. Numerical results from climate models (Task 2)

Table 2.2 Available environment data sources for the Fram Strait along 79°N latitude.

Data source	Period	Range	Number of stations	Comments
Arctic Oceanography Atlas	1950-1989	11°W to 11°E	9	Summer and winter season decadal means and total means
AOGC97-ctd	16/9/1997	3°E – 6°E	7	Cross section of meso scale eddy, high depth resolution (1m) down to bottom
AOGC97-SEASOAR	14/9/1997	2.45°- 9.15°E	53	Cross section of meso scale eddy, high resolution of range and 1 m depth resolution down to 200m
POLARSTERN	25-30/3/ 1993	11°W – 2.147°E	7	Cross-section of meso scale eddy, variable resolution down to bottom. (Used mainly by Esipov and Naugol'nykh)
Climate simulations (MPI)	1950– 2050	18.7°W -		Monthly means for the whole period. 1950 – 1975 is “spin up” period.

2.2.2 Averaged environmental data

The main source is the Arctic Oceanography Atlas, including a joint data set of Russian and western observations in the Arctic Ocean. Here data from many different sources have been interpolated, merged and averaged to a fixed grid in terms of decadal means for the summer and winter seasons, and averaged for the whole period 1950 – 1989. In this data set all short-term variations are averaged out. As a part of Task 1 data for the track along the Fram Strait along 79°N was extracted and saved on a CD-rom. For practical use these data sets were imported into Matlab and interpolated in two dimensions. Together with a detailed map of the bathymetry along 79°N this data can be translated to environmental data files fitting the different acoustical propagation models (OASES, RAM and RAY). The original data set yields temperature, salinity and density. From this sound speed has been calculated using Medwin's formula (Clay and Medwin 1977):

$$c = 1449.2 + 4.6t - 0.0555t^2 + 0.00029t^3 + (1.34 - 0.01t)(s - 35) + 0.016p,$$

where c is sound speed in m/s, t is temperature in degrees Celsius, s is salinity in parts per thousand and p is pressure in mbar.

Typical sound speed profiles for historical environments in the Fram Strait is shown in Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2, for summer and winter seasons respectively, as a mean of the decades 1950s through 1980s, as prepared in Task 1. Both individual profiles and color maps of the interpolated SSPs are shown, for clarity. The range is referenced to 11°W. The sound speed profile depends on temperature, salinity and static pressure (depth). In these waters both temperature and salinity is strongly varying in the surface region, particularly in the upper 200 m. The main variation is in vertical direction, but because of the two opposing currents, EGC and WSC, and the partial ice cover, the Fram Strait also show much stronger horizontal variation of the sound speed that usually found in Arctic Waters.

Figure 2.1 Sound speed profile along 79° N for the mean of summers 1950 through 1980s. **Left:** raw ssp-profiles, offset by 3 m/s for each station from Greenland side towards Svalbard (sound speed axis is correct only for the first (leftmost) profile). **Right:** Colormap of the same interpolated and with bathymetry added.

Figure 2.2 As Figure 2.1 for the mean of winters 1950 through 1980s.

As evident from these figures there is a large difference between typical summer and winter

profiles. The winter SSPs has a minimum at the surface, which results in a surface duct for the sound, extending down to about 200 m, depending on the range. Near the Greenland side there is a deeper duct, centered at about 600 m, but this seems to disappear as one approaches the Svalbard side. The summer SSPs has a very shallow surface duct, typically extending down to 50 m only. However, there is also another duct appearing below this, centered near a depth of 100 m. The extent of this duct widens as one approaches Svalbard, and it finally disappears or is overtaken by a new deeper duct appearing near 600 m depth. In both situations, the profiles below 1000 m seem to be very stable and alike.

The variation of SSP between decades is demonstrated in Figure 2.3 and Figure 2.4. In Figure 2.3 the change of the sound speed in the deepest profile (at 293 km) is shown as difference between summer means, and winter means, while Figure 2.4 shows the difference between summer and winter sound speeds in the same profile at the same decade, respectively.

Figure 2.3 Difference in sound speed between decades, at the deepest profile (293 km). Left: Summers 50 to 80. Right: Winters 50 to 80.

Figure 2.4 Difference in sound speed between seasons in the same decade, at the deepest profile (293 km).

In Figure 2.3 we notice that both summers and winters differences follow the same basic pattern: In the 50s a higher sound speed is found in the upper 1000m than in the 60s; The 60s have a somewhat higher sound speed in the layer 50 – 200 m than in the 70s, while somewhat lower in the layer 200 – 1000 m; The 70s sound speeds are generally lower than the 80s speeds, except very close to the surface. The variations from summer to winter seasons shown in Figure 2.4 all show the same trend: The sound speeds in summers are generally higher than in the winters down to about 1000 m. It is also evident, however, that the difference has become smaller in recent times: In the 50s the mean difference in the layer 100 – 500 m was about 4 m/s, while it is less than 2 m/s in the 80s. In the deeper layers there is little systematic variation to be seen.

2.2.3 *Meso scale eddy data sets*

Meso scale eddies typically have diameters 20 – 50 km, and lifetimes (passage times) 20 – 30 days. Vertically they extend down to 500-1000m, although the most significant variations are confined to the upper 200 m or so. A limited set of field data has been available for investigating the influence of meso scale eddies on sound propagation. In Task 1 results from the AOGC97 expedition have been tabulated, yielding 2 data sets. One is based on CTD measurements down to 2500 m at 7 stations along 79° N latitude from 3° E to 6° E taken September 16 1997. The other is based on SEASOAR measurements down to about 275 m at 53 stations from 2.75° E to 9.25° E taken September 14 1997. The third set is from the POLARSTERN expedition in March 1993, yielding 7 stations from 11° W to 2.14° E along 79° N latitude, down to 3600m at the deepest.

The raw AOGC97 data from is plotted in Figure 2.5. The finest structure is shown in the SEASOAR data (Figure 2.5, left). Here the depth resolution is about 2 m, and the range resolution about 3 km (note that in Figure 5, left, the two leftmost profiles have been located 30 m too high, so that the cool part actually extends deeper than it appears in this figure). The dark blue color indicates missing data, not the actual depth profile. The ctd-data from the same expedition is shown in Figure 2.5– right. Here depth resolution is about 1 m, but the range resolution is coarser, about 11 km. The same color-map has been used in these figures so a direct comparison of the features is possible. We recognize easily the correspondence between these two data sets, to the extent that they overlap. It does appear that during the two days separating the data sets some cold water has moved eastwards near 3° E in the upper 60 m. Because of this, and the overlap being only partial, it has proved difficult to merge these two data sets by interpolation.

The POLARSTERN data shown in Figure 2.6 has been interpolated, and is somewhat misleading at some depths since the bathymetry is not included. The data is interesting because it covers the western half of the Fram Strait. It also shows that the vertical penetration of the meso scale eddy extends to below 1000 m (right half of the figure).

Figure 2.5 Sound speed profiles showing meso scale activity - from the AOGC97 expedition September 97. Left: SEASOAR data, taken on 14/09. Right: CTD-data taken on 16/09.

Figure 2.6 POLARSTERN sound speed profile data showing meso scale activity, taken in March 1993.

The SEASOAR data was used in Chapter 7 for studying stability of rays during the passage of a meso scale eddy, as described below. The POLARSTERN data was used similarly for ray stability study and for prospecting inversion techniques, as described in Chapter 5-6.

2.2.4 Meso scale eddy simulation

In order to simulate the passage of a meso scale eddy the AOGC97 SEASOAR data set was interpolated on a regular grid and the mean sound speed subtracted so that a grid of sound speed differences resulted. The grid cell size was 1.77 km by 2 m. A margin was then added to the bottom part and to each side, in which the data is tapered by linear interpolation. This is to avoid artificial discontinuities when merging the meso scale data and the mean environmental data sets. The depth/width of the margins may be adjusted.

The final merging was obtained by interpolating the selected averaged environmental data set to the same grid size and selecting a range for the entry point of the western edge of the meso scale data. The data sets were then simply added after adjusting the amplitude of the meso scale data with a factor (0-1), in order to simulate various stages during the passage.

2.2.5 Ambient noise in the Fram Strait

An extensive study of ambient acoustic noise in the marginal ice zone was reported in H. Sagen (1998). Two of the cases studied there are relevant for the Fram Strait. The first is based on data from MIZEX 85 taken April 30, 1985 near 78° N, 1° E. 21 sono-buoys were deployed, 7 at 18 m depth, 7 at 122 m, and 7 at 305 m. The water depth is between 2000 and 3000 m. The area covered is near the ice edge and contains open sea, diffuse ice, compact ice and interior pack ice.

The wind was 3-5 m/s and directed parallel to the ice edge. The surface wave field outside the ice edge was dominated by short waves of period 3-4 s. The significant wave height was less than 0.5 m. Figure 2.7 show averaged ambient noise level as a function of distance from the ice edge, at 122 m depth, for frequencies 40, 100, 315 and 1000 Hz. At 40 and 100 Hz there is no systematic variation in the noise level with distance, but the variability is higher inside the ice zone. The maximum level at 40 Hz was 89 dB, while the level in the open sea was near 84 dB. At 100 Hz the level is near 82 dB. As frequencies increase a peak become more pronounced near the ice edge. The peak values lie near 74 dB at 315 Hz and 65 dB at 1000 Hz, while the corresponding values in open sea are 71 dB and 60 dB, respectively. These results indicate typical noise levels during calm weather conditions.

Somewhat rougher conditions are exemplified in the second data set. This is from MIZEX 87 taken April 2, 1987, near 78° N, 4° W. 16 sono-buoys were deployed partly inside the ice pack and in the open sea. The water depth is sloping downwards on the continental shelf towards east from about 500 m at the western part of the area. The wind speed observed some 30 miles outside the ice edge decreased from 9 m/s to 5 m/s around noon, at the same time as the wind direction changed from northeast to north. Inside the ice edge the wind speed was 7 m/s from the north all the time. 6 km inside the pack ice the observed wave height was between 0.7 and 1.5 m. The averaged ambient noise levels at 122 m depth are plotted as a function of distance from the ice edge in Figure 2.8, for frequencies 40, 100, 315 and 1000 Hz. Also here the noise level seems independent of the distance from the ice edge, except very close to it. The level lies around 89 dB, with a maximum of 93 dB at the ice edge. It must be noted that the buoy farthest out from the ice edge actually lies close to a separate tongue of ice in the process of disintegration, and thus may be exposed to noise sources separate from the main ice edge. Thus, the noise level in open water far from the ice edge might be lower than shown here. At the other frequencies (100, 300, 1000 Hz) the noise level in open sea is 89 dB, 80 dB and 70 dB, respectively. Thus, under these weather conditions the noise levels are typically some 6 dB \pm 1dB higher than in the first case.

The two cases are plotted in Figure 2.9. They best fit curves (2. order polynomial) show basically the same trend, but is shifted 5.7 dB with respect to each other. It is to be noted that the noise level is markedly higher than what is customary in open sea, due to the closeness to the ice front. It is reasonable to believe that these conditions may be regarded as indicative of worst case situations to be encountered in the Fram Strait.

Figure 2.7 Plot of averaged ambient noise level observed on April 30, 1985 at 122 m depth as a function of least distance from the ice edge.

Figure 2.8 Plot of averaged ambient noise level at 122 m, obtained on April 2, 1987, according to least distance from the ice edge.

Figure 2.9. Observed noise level versus frequency in the Fram Strait.

2.3 Acoustical simulation models

Several acoustical simulation models were used in this report, the most important of which are: OASES, RAM and RAY, which are briefly described below.

OASES is a general purpose computer code for modeling seismo-acoustic propagation in horizontally stratified waveguides using wavenumber integration. It is basically an upgraded version of the SAFARI (Seismo-Acoustic Fast field Algorithm for Range Independent environments) model developed by F.B. Jensen and H. Schmidt (1985) at SACLANTCEN, La Spezia, Italy. It contains a number of features such as modules for calculating reflection coefficients, transmission loss, wide-band transfer functions (in 2D and 3D) etc., and a post-processing tool for obtaining pulse shapes. Thus, it is able to cope with very complicated environments, with a number of layers including shear waves. It also contains a module for extending computations to range-dependent environments. However, it turned out that the available super-computer (ORIGIN 2000) met with memory-allocation problems when we applied it to long range propagation above 600 km. We have been unable to resolve these problems.

RAM is a computer code developed by Michael D. Collins at NRL, Washington based on the parabolic equation. It does include provisions for taking into account complicated bottom structures with shear waves, and range independent environments. However it lacks ability to account for ice layers at the surface, and surface waves. It has proved to be very efficient for computing transmission loss with long range propagation, and is a useful tool for optimizing sound source and hydrophone locations. In this project we developed a Matlab code for post processing.

RAY is a computer code developed by J.B. Bowlin, J.L. Spiesberger, T. F. Duda and L.E. Freitag at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution. It is a very flexible ray-tracing code for 2D range dependent environments, but does not account for sophisticated bottom or surface properties (bottom type: absorbing or reflecting). It has proved very useful for assessing long range arrival times and expected ray amplitudes, in particular in studies of the seasonal variations of the environmental conditions.

2.4 References

- Bourke, R.H. and A.R. Parsons (1993), "Ambient noise characteristics of the northwestern Barents Sea", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **94**, 2799-2808.
- Clay, C.S. and H. Medwin (1977), *Acoustical Oceanography*, Wiley-Interscience, New York 1977.
- Dyer, I. *et al.* (1987), P.H. Dahl, A.B. Baggeroer, P.N. Mikhaelevsky, "Ocean dynamics and acoustic fluctuations in the Fram Strait marginal ice zone", *Science* **236**, 435-436.
- Jin G. *et al.* (1993), J.F. Lynch, R. Pawlowicz, P. Wadhams, "Effects on sea ice cover on acoustic travel times with applications to the Greenland Sea tomography experiment", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **94**, 1044-1057.
- Johannessen, O.M. *et al.* (1987), J.A. Johannessen, E. Svendsen, R.A. Shuchman, W.J. Campbell, E.G. Josberger, "Ice-edge effects in the Fram strait marginal ice zone", *science* **436**, 427-429.

- Johannessen, J.A. *et al.* (1987), O.M. Johannessen, E. Svendsen, R.A. Shuchman, T. Manley, W.J. Campbell, E.G. Josberger, S. Sandven, J.C. Gascard, T. Olaussen, K. Davidson, J. Van Leer, "Mesoscale eddies in the Fram Strait marginal ice zone during the 1983 and 1984 marginal ice zone experiments", *J. Geophys. Res.* **92**, 6754-6772.
- Johannessen, O.M. *et al.* (1992), H. Sagen, Ø. Nesse, I. Engelsen, S. Sandven, "Ambient noise generated by ice-ocean jets, eddies and tidal current in the marginal ice zone", in "Proceedings of the European conference on Underwater Acoustics", M. Weydert (ed.), Elsevier 1992, pp. 28-38.
- Kowalik Z. and A.Y. Proshutinsky (1994), "The arctic ocean tides", in *The Polar Oceans and Their Role in shaping the Global Environment*, O.M. Johannessen, R.D. Muench and J.E. Overland (eds.), Geophysical Monograph 85, American Geophysical Union, pp. 137-158.
- Lynch, J.F. *et al.* (1996), G. Jin, R. Pawlowicz, D. Ray, A. Plueddeman, C.-S. Chin, J.H. Miller, R.H. Bourke, A.r. Parsons, R. Muench, "acoustic travel-time perturbations due to shallow water waves and internal waves in the Barents Sea Polar front: theory and experiment", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **99**, 803-821.
- Makris N.C. and I. Dyer (1991), "Environmental correlates of Arctic ice edge noise", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **90**, 3288-3298.
- Mellberg, L.E. *et al.* (1987), O.M. Johannessen, D. Connors, G. Botseas, D. Browning, "Acoustic propagation in the western Greenland Sea frontal zone", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **89**, 2144-2156.
- Schmidt, H. and F.B. Jensen (1985), *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **77**, 813-825.
- Sandven, S. and O.M. Johannessen, (1987), "High frequency internal wave observations in the marginal ice zone", *J. Geophys. Res.* **92**, 6911-6920.
- Sutton, P.S. *et al.* (1993), P.F. Worcester, G. Masters, B.D. Cornelle, J.F. Lynch, "Ocean mixed layers and acoustic propagation in the Greenland Sea", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **94**, 1517-1526.
- Worcester, P.F. *et al.* (1993), J.F. Lynch, W.M.L. Morawitz, R. Pawlowicz, P.J. Sutton, B.D. Cornelle, O.M. Johannessen, W.H. Munk, W.B. Owens, R. Shuchman, R.C. Spindel, "Evolution of large scale temperature field in the Greenland Sea during 1988-89 tomographic measurements", *Geophys. Res. Letters* **20**, 2211-2214.

3. Topographical influence on the acoustic insonification of the Fram Strait for optimal receiver and source configuration (Subtask 4.1)

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by NIERSC personnel.

The calculations have been carried out using OASES, RAM and RAY models. The horizontal resolution in the environmental input to the acoustic models is around 50km, which is the resolution in the US-Russian oceanographic data. The track along 79°N in the Fram Strait has 9 sectors. The sound speed fields used as input to the range dependent OASES, RAM and RAY models are generated from oceanographic data obtained from the US-Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean. The sound speed input has been established for summer and winter means conditions for 1950s, 1960s, 1970s and 1980s. The RAY and RAM programs are provided with an interpolated sound speed field. Bathymetry is available from TerrianBase for use in RAY and RAM.

3.1 Study the influence of the smooth bottom on acoustic propagation in the Fram Strait

In this study the acoustic transmission losses have been calculated by the RAM (Range-dependent Acoustic Model) model. Simulations have been performed for the means winter and summer 1980s conditions. Appropriate sound speed fields used as input are presented at Figure 3.1. For these studies the different frequencies (20, 100, 250 and 500 Hz) are used. The different source (within and outside the duct) at 18, 60, 122, 250 and 500m depths and the different source/receiver locations (on the shelf and off the shelf) have been considered.

The transmission loss as a function of depth and range is strongly influenced by the depth of the source, location of the source relatively to shelf and frequency. If the low frequency (20 Hz) source is located in the beginning of the acoustic path (for all considered source depths) the acoustic energy is generally trapped within the upper 1000m layer of the water. This is because the bottom at the shelf attenuated the deeper going modes strongly. These simulations are indicated that the best signal to noise ratio for the source at the shallow shelf location is obtained when the source is positioned at 122m depth. (Comparing results of the simulations are presented at Figure 3.2-upper and 3.2-lower). (the same result has been obtained by OASES – Annual progress report N2). When the position of the source is 50km closer to the deep part of the strait the depth of the acoustic insonification increasing down to 1500m (Figure 3.3). Higher frequency (100 Hz) results in that more energy trapped within the surface duct (Figure 3.4). Other simulations have shown that by moving the source to the location off the shelf the acoustic energy is transmitted through the whole water column at low frequency (20 Hz).

In Figure 3.5 plotted the situation when the source is positioned off the shelf at 60m below sea surface and for frequency 100Hz. This causes some of the acoustic energy to be trapped within the surface duct. By increasing the frequency up to 500Hz, as present at Figure 3.6, the acoustic pattern becomes ray like with strong convergence and shadow zones. By lowering the source to 500m the convergence and shadowing effects becomes weaker (Figure 3.7). In cases with strong shadowing effects one need to plan experiments carefully with respect to the choice of the receivers locations in order to have good enough signal to noise ratios. The results of the simulations have shown that the source/receiver positions should be off the shelf in order to avoid that the deep going part of the acoustic field is influenced by bathymetry, and that the deep source gives a better insonification of the water-masses for all frequencies. The seasonal (winter/summer) changes do not influence on the general pattern of the acoustic energy distribution at the low (20Hz) frequency (Comparing results of simulations are presented at Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.8) (the same result has been obtained by OASES – Annual progress

report N2). But at higher frequency it is observed an essential difference in the structure of the acoustic field between winter and summer condition (Comparing results of the simulations are presented at Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.9). In particular the front between cold water in the eastern side of the Fram Strait and warm water in the western one is detected. By plotting the transmission loss as a function of depth and range at a given receivers positions, at 240 km from the source, a good enough signal to noise ratio for low frequency is found in the upper 1000m of the ocean while for high frequencies in the upper 500m.

3.2 Reflection loss

Study the influence sedimentation on acoustic propagation has been performed by OASES model. When the source is located on the shelf the bathymetry becomes important boundary condition and significantly influence on acoustic propagation. After several bounces the sound has been exposed to several reflection and scattering losses. In this study only the characteristics of specular reflection is considered. Simulations have been performed for the winter 1980s conditions. The reflection loss has been calculated as a function of grazing angle and frequency (from 1 to 1000Hz) for 20, 50, 100 and 200 m sediment layer thickness. The parameters of the sediment layer and sub-bottom used for reflection loss calculations are presented in Table 1. These parameters were taken from Finn B. Jensen, William A. Kuperman, Michael B. Potter and Henrik Schmidt book “Computational Ocean Acoustic”. Results of the calculations are presented in Figure 3.10, where the white color corresponds to the total reflection. The reflection loss function depends significantly on the frequency with respect to grazing angle. Furthermore, the results of calculations finds out a strong sensitivity in the reflection coefficient function with respect to frequency to changes in sediment layer thickness.

For the thinner sediment layer (20m) at the low frequencies (around 50Hz and less) the sediment layer thickness is thin compared to the acoustic wavelength (32m) making the layer transparent to the incident wave. The reflection properties are dominated by the critical angle $\theta_{c2} \approx \cos^{-1}(c_1/c_2) = 36^\circ$ of the sub-bottom, whereas for the higher frequencies a series of “resonance ridges” of high loss appear, asymptotically approaching the sediment layer critical angle $\theta_{c1} \approx \cos^{-1}(c/c_1) = 24.4^\circ$ due to the acoustic wavelength becomes comparable with sediment layer thickness. Total reflection occurs at all frequencies for grazing angles less then the sediment layer critical angle = 24.4° . Increasing the sediment layer thickness to 50m results to decreasing the frequency (around 20 Hz) when the sediment layer thin compared to the acoustic wavelength (80m). For the thickest sediment layer (200m) the reflection properties of the sub-bottom practically do not influence or only slightly influence on acoustic propagation. On the other hand, decreasing of the sediment layer thickness leads to increasing the frequency when sub-bottom reflection properties dominate.

Table 3.1 Bottom parameters for the reflection loss calculations.

Layer	Layers thickness H (m)	<u>Sound speed</u>		<u>Attenuation</u>		Density
		C _c (m/s)	C _s (m/s)	γ _c (dB/Λ)	γ _s (dB/Λ)	ρ (g/sm ³)
Water	∞	1457	0	0	0	1
Sediment (silt)	20, 50, 100, 200	1600	400	0.2	0.5	1.8
Sub-bottom (sand)	∞	1800	600	0.1	0.2	2.0

According to the results we conclude that:

- For the source at the shallow shelf location the best signal to noise ratio is obtained when the source is positioned at 122m depth.
- The sources/receivers positions should be off the shelf in order to avoid that the deeper going part of the acoustic field is influenced by bathymetry.
- Deep source gives a better insonification of the watermasses for high frequencies.
- Calculation of the transmission loss as a function of the depth and range at high frequency can be use for monitoring oceanographic changes.
- Sedimentation significantly influence on acoustic propagation when the source is located at the shallow shelf.
- With respect to a good enough signal to noise ratio for low frequency receivers should be positioned in the upper 1000m of the ocean while for high frequencies in the upper 500m.

Figure 3.1 Sound speed fields derived from oceanographic data included on the Joint US-Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean for means summer (upper) and winter (lower) conditions 1980s across the Fram Strait long 79°N.

Figure 3.2 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Upper: Source depth = 122m. Lower: Source depth = 18m. Frequency = 20Hz.

Figure 3.3 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =20Hz.

Figure 3.4 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =100Hz.

Figure 3.5 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 60m. Frequency =100Hz.

Figure 3.6 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 60m. Frequency =500Hz.

Figure 3.7 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean winter conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 500m. Frequency =500Hz.

Figure 3.8 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean summer conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =20Hz.

Figure 3.9 Transmission loss as a function of depth and range for mean summer conditions in the Fram Strait along 79°N. Source depth = 122m. Frequency =100Hz.

20m

50m

100m

200m

Figure 3.10 Reflection loss as a function of grazing angle and frequency calculated by OASES for varying sediment layer thickness.

4. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes (Subtask 4.2)

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by NIERSC personnel.

The RAY-model has been used for the calculations of the eigenrays and travel times of the eigenrays for means summer and winter conditions for each decades (1950s, 1960s, 1970s and 1980s) and for the different source (60, 122, 250 and 500m) and receiver (60, 122, 250 and 500m) depths. The launch angles from -15 to $+15$ degrees and 1000 ray were shot. Examples of the sound speed fields (winter and summer 1980s) used for the calculations are presented in Figure 3.1.

A ray with given launch angle will trace the water masses according to the horizontal and vertical gradients present in oceanographic input data. The average sound speed along ray is closely related to the temperature and salinity conditions along the path. Eigenrays are rays which goes from the source to a given receiver position. The plots of the eigenrays found at 240 km from the source for winter and summer averaged conditions (1950s) for shallow (60m) and deep (500m) source/receiver locations are presented at Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2. It is clearly seen that for deep source/receiver position (500m) the eigenrays are tracing the same water-masses. Also RAY calculate the arrival time and path length for each eigenray, those parameters are used to find the averaged sound speed for each eigenray.

Arrival times of eigenrays found at 240 km from the source at selected receiver depths (60, 122, 250 and 500 m) for means winter and summer conditions (averaged for 40 years - 1950s-1980s) are plotted at Figure 4.3. Rays passing through the cold upper water masses are slower than the rays passing through the deeper and warmer water masses. The biggest difference between fast summer and slower winter rays is observed for shallowest source/receiver configuration at 60 and 122m depth. While for deep source/receiver positions at 250m and especially at 500 m depth eigenrays arrival times for winter period to come nearer to eigenrays arrival times for summer due to the rays are going through the same water-masses.

Results of the calculations averaged sound speed along eigenrays found at the receiver at 240 km from the source for the means winter and summer conditions for the each decades 1950s, 1960s, 1970s and 1980s are plotted, at Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5, for different source/receiver locations. In the case when both source and receiver are positioned at 60m depth for two decades (1950s, 1960s) the differences between averaged sound speed for winter and summer times are clear (Figure 4.5, upper plot). During winter time the eigenrays have lower sound speed and greater spread in sound speeds than found in summer, because in winter time a high number of eigenrays are trapped within the upper 100-150m of the ocean arrives at receiver. For the two last decades (1970s, 1980s) these differences becomes smaller because of emerging faster rays penetrating deeper during the winter times, and winter conditions becomes more similar to summer conditions. By moving the receiver deeper (at 500m depth) the number of eigenrays is reduced during winter time due to that slow eigenrays trapped within upper layer are disappeared (Figure 4.5, lower plot). For such source/receiver configuration the eigentays are tracing upper 1000-1200m water in both seasons. The situation for the case when source is positioned at 500m depth and receiver is positioned at 60m depth is the same as when source and receiver positioned at 60m (Figure 4.4, upper plot). But the number of eigenrays is considerably decreased. When both source and receiver are positioned at 500m depth (Figure 4.4, lower plot) the plot indicates a stable situation because the rays have gone trough the same water-masses (around upper 1000 – 1200 m of the ocean).

Figure 4.1 Plot of the eigenrays found at 240 km from the source. Means winter 1950s conditions. Source depth = Receiver depth = 60m (upper). Source depth = Receiver depth = 500m (lower).

Figure 4.2 Plot of the eigenrays found at 240 km from the source. Means summer 1950s conditions. Source depth = Receiver depth = 60m (upper). Source depth = Receiver depth = 500m (lower).

Figure 4.3 Arrival times for eigenrays found at 240km from the source vs selected receiver depths (60, 122, 250 and 500m) (mean1950s-1980s); blue ‘*’ - winter, red ‘o’- summer; Source depths=60m(a); =122m(b); =250m(c); =500m(d).

Figure 4.4 Averaged sound speed along eigenrays found at 240 km from the source positioned 60m below the sea surface for winter (blue) and summer (red) averaged conditions for each decades (1950s, 1960s, 1970s, 1980s). Receiver depth = 60m (upper) and 500m (lower).

Figure 4.5 Averaged sound speed along eigenrays found at 240 km from the source positioned 500m below the sea surface for winter (blue) and summer (red) averaged conditions for each decades (1950s, 1960s, 1970s, 1980s). Receiver depth = 60m (upper) and 500m (lower).

According to the results we conclude that:

For the shallow source:

- The seasonal variations (implying temperature and salinity variations) are clearly observed for all selected receiver depths.
- Less variations seen for the lowest receiver (at 500m depth).
- Summer conditions are more stable than the winter conditions.

For the deep source:

- Some seasonal variation seen for the shallow receivers (at 60 and 122m depths).
- More stable situation with respect to seasonal changes is observed for the deep receiver locations (at 250 and 500m depths).

Travel time variations can be used for monitoring temperature and general structure changes.

5. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to temperature changes using the cumulative sum and collective arrival time approach (Subtask 4.2)

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by Russian subcontractors.

5.1 Introduction

Problem of temperature variation measurement by acoustic means is considered excluding the influence stream velocity. The temperature field distribution in Arctic Ocean is rather inhomogeneous, and its research demands comprehensive tomographic methods. However, in the first stage we simplify the problem and shall consider the time variation of the signal propagation along the appropriate rays under environmental conditions typical of Fram Strait in the presence of homogeneous heating of the upper ocean water layer.

The process of sound wave propagation in the Fram Strait is strongly dependent on the variable environmental conditions. In the Marginal Ice Zone, typical mesoscale eddies have diameters of 20 to 50 km, periods and lifetimes of at least 20 days, and vertical structures penetrating to depths of 500 to 1000 m, with the most significant variations over the first 100 m and advection rates of 5 to 15 km per day [1]. These inhomogeneities have an influence on time propagation of the sound signal, changing it randomly, therefore giving rise to background noise in average time signal propagation measurement, which in turn depends on water layer temperature.

It should be noted that eddies in the Fram Strait have relatively short lifetimes, length scales, and time scales with respect to mid-ocean eddies [2,3], which allows us to eliminate the random noise influence on signal time-of-flight measurement by averaging with respect to the pathway and the time of measurement. Strong temperature changes often occur in the region of eddy, causing strong sound speed gradients and consequent anomalous acoustic propagation [4,5].

Normal modes and rays are commonly employed representations of the acoustic field generated by a point source in water. Since most underwater acoustic applications in signal frequency range from several hundred to one thousand Hertz (which are optimal for moderate range ocean-acoustic probing at distances of hundred kilometers in order), the variation of the refractive properties of the medium is small over the acoustic wavelength, and one can use geometric acoustic [6]. In spite of some computational problems of the field evaluation near caustics and turning points, the ray representation requires a much smaller number of terms than the mode representation. The basic parameter for ray acoustics calculations is the sound-speed value or refractive index distribution over the ocean in the area of interest, which is in general a function of all three spatial coordinates and time.

Let's consider the average temperature change in the upper layer of the ocean. The oceanographic model is presented in the next section. Numerical models for acoustic signal propagation in the region under consideration are then developed with different subsurface layer temperatures. Two approaches are used. At the first step we used an approach based on selection of stable arrivals, which don't change their type of propagation under variable environment condition. We can determine there the travel time variation of the stable arrivals due to the temperature variation. Another approach consists of defining the trends in the signal arrival time spectrum caused by the temperature changes by computing averaged parameters of the arriving signal ensemble [7,8]. Arrival time fluctuations due to ocean inhomogeneity are obtained both by computational experiments and by approximate analytical estimates. Comparison of the magnitude of fluctuations with the regular arrival time variations induced by temperature changes, leads to estimates of the sensitivity of the method.

5.2 Oceanographic model

Fram Strait cross section along 79°N latitude was chosen for the modeling. Positions of the acoustic transmitter (T) and receiver (R) are shown at Figure 5.1. Figure 5.2 shows the isolines of sound velocity in the vertical cross-section of the strait along the sound path-way, obtained by parabolic interpolation of the oceanography measurement made by RV "Polarstern" expedition in March, 1993. The corresponding equation for the sound speed dependence on the oceanographic parameters is in m/sec:

$$c = 1448.96 + 4.591T - 0.05304T^2 + 0.0002374T^3 + 1.340(S-35) + 0.01630D + (1.675 \times 10^{-7})D^2,$$

where T is the temperature in degrees Celsius, S is the salinity in parts per thousand, and D is the depth in meters.

It is seen from Figure 5.2, that larger variations of the sound velocity on this pathway were observed in the upper 500 m. Let us assume that the ocean inhomogeneities, which lead to sound velocity changing vary randomly in time and space. The horizontal spatial scale of the sound-speed inhomogeneity is of the order of 10 km. When we consider the inhomogeneities of the sound velocity as random variations we certainly simplify the problem. It is clear that some of the measured ocean inhomogeneities will not vary in time and in space; for example, ocean current inhomogeneities can be regarded as stationary, hence, will not affect the variations of the process of sound wave propagation.

The position of the source was chosen in such a way that the selected rays will not change their type due to variation of the ocean environment. The most convenient rays are those emitted by the source at the angles of moderate slope. These rays are reflected several times from the surface, crossing the subsurface layer, where most of the water temperature variation takes place, but do not touch the bottom. We don't consider the bottom reflected rays because they strong scattering and dampening. Beside this the bottom acoustic features are not usually known in detail and use of bottom reflected rays are undesirable.

More gently sloping rays can have different number of surface contacts for slightly different hydrographic conditions. In accordance with the Snell's law the ray will cross a surface if the sound velocity at the depth of the lower point of the ray turn exceeds the velocity on the surface and in the core of the eddy. For such a limiting velocity we take the value 1475 m/s. In the absence of inhomogeneities, such a velocity is observed at a depth of about 1800 m. Therefore we choose the deepest part of Fram Strait cross section with the depth more then 2000 m for the modeling. The source is at a depth of 500 m, and the receiver is at a depth of 300 m. Other positions of the receiver were also considered. Where a subsurface sound channel exists, the positioning of the source at a smaller depth would produce the large number of changeable rays with shallow turn points. These rays are difficult to use due to large variations of the numbers of reflections from the surface.

Then two ensembles of sound speed distributions were constructed. One was obtained by the horizontal shifting the whole hydrographic field to simulate oceanography variation and to estimate numerically the signal arrival time fluctuation. Another set of profiles was constructed to model ocean subsurface layer heating. It was supposed that the temperature changes take place in the upper 200 m of the ocean, namely that the average temperature of this layer increased by 1-3°C. Corresponding sound speed dependence on temperature variation was calculated according the equation

$$\Delta c \approx 4.591\Delta T + 0.10608T\Delta T, \quad (2)$$

which was obtained from (1). This value was added to the initial sound speed profiles in the upper 200 m subsurface layer.

Figure 5.1 Fram Strait acoustical path.

Figure 5.2 Sound speed profile in Fram Strait (March, 1993).

5.3 Travel time variation

Statistical ensembles of the sound-speed fields were constructed from specific parts of the general oceanographic data distribution presented in Figure 5.2. The space between source and

receiver forms a stationary path of 200 km. Figure 5.3 shows an example of stable configuration of paths for which the acoustical signal is touching the sea surface four or five times. Inhomogeneity variation on the acoustical pathway was modeled by shifting of the environment pattern (Figure 5.2) with respect to both source-receiver and bottom configuration with 10 km step of each. 11 patterns of the environmental configurations on the path of 200 km were realized that way. The total environmental shift was 100 km or three spatial intervals of environmental correlation. Such a procedure is useful for randomizing the signal time-of-flight computation results to get the fluctuations of the signal arrival times due to ocean inhomogeneities. The positions of source and receiver were not changed with respect to the bottom profile during this procedure.

Mean statistical values calculated in accord to described procedure are shown at Figure 5.3 Stable configuration of 4s and 5s rays along the path.

Table 5.1.

Figure 5.3 Stable configuration of 4s and 5s rays along the path.

Table 5.1 Arrival time of signals.

Receiver depth (m)	Mean value	RMS arrival time
	5s arrival (s)	fluctuations (ms)
100	137.027	32.0
200	137.014	29.0
300	137.003	27.1

Arrival 5s is transmitted upward from the source and at more gentle slopes than arrival 4s. Therefore it propagates in the upper inhomogeneous layer for longer than arrival 4s, which produces increased signal fluctuations along this path. The table data demonstrate that the arrival time fluctuations of along the moderate steep rays due to mesoscale inhomogeneities are of the order of 10 ms and as we shall see later are comparable to that produced by the internal wave.

Travel times for 4s arrival and 5s arrival were calculated for different temperature of the upper 200 m subsurface layer. The results are shown at Figure 5.4. Increasing the average temperature leads to subsurface sound refraction. Calculation shows that arrival 5s remains as a stable one in the rather restricted interval of temperature variation (about 0.5°C), while the 4s arrival is proved to be stable in a more vast area of temperature change. The slopes of the curves correspond to gradients of $29 \text{ ms}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4s arrival and $37 \text{ ms}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5s arrival. A smaller degree of temperature variation can be measured using the rays with gentle slopes as long as they are stable enough with respect to effects of mesoscale inhomogeneities. However in such a case the exit angles should be sufficiently large to prevent type of the ray changing due to mesoscale environment variation. The ocean heating evaluation accuracy depends on the signal processing procedure. For one travel time measurement, the error will be of the order of the root mean square of the signal fluctuation, or (20-30) ms (see Table 1), corresponding to a temperature measurement error of about 1°C . The ocean probing in a time scale, large compared with the time scale of mesoscale variability, gives an opportunity to reject travel time variation due to mesoscale effect in signal storage procedure. In this case the random measurement error will decrease as the inverse square root of the number of statistically independent measurements. The evaluation of accuracy can be performed on the time scales of the ocean warming and the mesoscale inhomogeneities. For the typical mesoscale eddies, having diameters of 20-50 km and drift rates of 5-15 km per day, one can estimate the time correlation interval for the environment variation in any cross section as about 3 days. In the case of homogeneous random process, the signal storage procedure can suppress the travel time fluctuation up to $(t/3)^{1/2}$ times, here t is time of monitoring or signal storage in days. Estimation shows that suppression could reach 10 times for a year observation or 30 times for a decade cycle. The accuracy of mean temperature measurement of 0.1°C per a year or 0.06°C per a decade cycle is sufficient to follow only seasonal variation of the environment.

Figure 5.4 Travel time variation as a function of temperature change for 4s and 5s arrivals. Curves 1, 2 and 3 correspond to receiver depth 100m, 200m, and 300m.

5.4 Cumulative signal storage

Another method of signal processing is to deal with signal as a whole, without considering that separate parts propagate along different rays. Increasing water temperature leads in general to decreasing propagation times. To detect this behavior against the noise background it is natural to use a statistical approach. One procedure is an algorithm based on cumulative sum consideration/ The cumulative summation procedure is widely used in seismology for investigation of the statistical spreading of earthquake shocks in time [9]. In our case we consider the cumulative sum with respect to the number of arrival times of the signal t_i corresponding to different rays. When one arranges the series from all the signal arrival times in order of increasing value $t_1 < t_2 < t_3 \dots < t_N$, the cumulative sum S can be written as

$$S(t) = \frac{1}{N} \begin{cases} 0 & t < t_1 \\ i & t \leq t < t_{i+1} \\ N & t > t_N \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The normalization factor $1/N$ is used to compare the results of the calculation for signal realizations with different numbers of rays. The procedure of cumulative sum computation is as follows:

- the signal threshold is defined;
- the appropriate amplitude of the signal propagating along the chosen rays is normalized to 1 if its value is higher than the threshold; otherwise it is set to 0;
- the normalized amplitude of each successive signal is added to the sum of normalized amplitudes of the preceding signals in order of signal arrival time;
- the total sum is normalized with respect to number of terms in the series. Thus the cumulative sum is computed corresponding to transient time function for the medium where the sound signal propagates.

Thus the cumulative sum corresponds to transfer function for the medium in which the signal propagates. Analysis of the cumulative sum is based on the computation of the linear regression coefficients of $S(t)$ with respect to the time t_i of the signal arrival. Another word, the coefficients a and b are defined for the expression $at_i + b$ in accord to the least-squares method of minimizing

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (S(t_i) - at_i - b)^2 \quad (4)$$

Regression lines of $S(t)$ are shown in Figure 5.5 as a function of signal arrival times for different temperatures of the layer. Figures indicate the subsurface layer temperature increase ΔT , ($\Delta T=0$ correspond to initial state of the ocean) and the hydrographic pattern shift. Two lines correspond to the initial sound velocity distribution and shifted at 30. Three other lines correspond to different amount of heating of the upper subsurface layer. It is seen from the plot that the slope of the lines is different from the random variation for temperature deviations above 1°C . Computations show that the slope of the cumulative sum as a function of time corresponds directly to the ocean layer temperature T . The regression line slope a as a function of water temperature is presented at Figure 5.6. The cumulative sum magnitude is normalized, therefore the slope of the regression line, shown at Figure 5.6, depends only upon the duration of the travel time difference $t_N - t_i$, which is proved in proportional to temperature change in upper ocean layer. The steep rays are the first to arrive and the axial rays are the last ones. For

the winter type of hydrographic environment the waveguide axis is located near the sea surface, so heating of subsurface layer hastens of the axial signal propagation and decreases the arrival signal pattern duration.

Figure 5.5 Cumulative sum regression lines versus signal arrival times for different subsurface layer temperature. Labels indicate the subsurface layer temperature increase ΔT and oceanographic pattern shift in km. Label (0°C, 0 km) corresponds to initial environmental realization, (0°C, 30 km) to that shifted at 30 km.

Figure 5.6 Regression line slope a as a function of water temperature. Solid line shows a linear approximation $a(\Delta T)$ dependence.

5.5 Collective arrivals time change

Advantages of stable rays approach to inverse the temperature change in cross section of the strait are related with the permanent following of travel time variation conditioned by the ocean inhomogeneities advection.

Disadvantages of this approach related with difficulties to find the stable arrivals for any given configuration source-receiver and seldom deep water stable rays penetration to upper ocean layer (four or five touching of the ocean surface on 200 km pathway) where mean value of heat and mass transport occurs. It is very difficult to found rays, which would be stable through the seasons and the years.

To overcome this disadvantage modified Collective Arrival Time (CAT) approach was used. The approach uses all possible arrivals, which realized in variable environment. The following procedure using the principals of maximum likelihood was developed to account a stable feature in collective arrival time:

1. Fix two successive realizations of arrivals which amplitude exceed the chosen threshold. Normalize amplitude of arrivals to 1.
2. Apply cross correlation procedure to define the time delay between correlated structures in the successive arrivals (position of the maximum of the function). It will be as an increment in collective time of correlated arrivals for successive signal realizations.
3. Integrate series of the increments to obtain travel time variation of the correlated structure of the signal. This travel time feature of the signal could be used for the subsequent inversion procedure described above.

More detail description of the method is presented in the next section. In similar way as the cumulative sum procedure was developed to follow the signal duration change in variable environment. In this case time differences between all possible arrivals are defined for successive realizations and after that the cross correlation procedure and integration as it is mentioned above, provides an opportunity to define the signal duration change as collective effect for all arrivals.

The next simple expressions show principal relations of the collective arrivals time change as well as cumulative sum change with the temperature in the ocean. For the collective arrival time change we have estimation

$$\Delta t \approx -\frac{L}{c^2} \Delta c = -\frac{L}{c^2} 4.59 \Delta T, \quad (5)$$

where L is length of the path and c is the mean value of the sound speed, ΔT is temperature increment averaged through the whole ocean layer. As to estimation of the signal duration, we define the travel time for the first arrival, which propagates mostly in deep ocean layer, as $t_1 = L/c_1$, where c_1 is deep ocean sound speed. Travel time for the slowest arrivals, which propagate in shallow water waveguide, can be estimated the same way as $t_N = L/c_N$, where c_N is shallow water sound speed. Mind the linear change of sound speed with the depth $c_1 = c_N(1+Dz_1)$, where z is depth of the deepest ray in km and $D = 0.012 \text{ km}^{-1}$ is a proportional coefficient, one could estimate the signal duration as

$$t_N - t_1 \approx L \frac{c_1 - c_N}{c_1 c_N} \approx LD \frac{z_1}{c_N(T)} \quad (6)$$

Therefore the signal duration change with the temperature, that is defined by cumulative sum

procedure, can be estimated as

$$\Delta(t_N - t_1) \approx LD \frac{z_1}{c_N^2} 4.59 \Delta T \quad (7)$$

Here ΔT_N is a temperature change in shallow water layer, where the slowest arrivals propagate with sound speed of c_N .

Figure 5.7 shows travel time variation cross the Fram Strait along 250 km path through the decades from 50s to 80s years. Joint U.S. - Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean [11] was used as a source of the environment seasonal data averaged for 50s, 60s, 70s and 80s decades. Modeling reveals the change in time propagation along stable ray, collective arrivals time and cumulative sum. Calculation shows the difference in travel time for summer and winter conditions in 0.2 sec, which corresponds to 0.3°C for the path of 250 km long, and this difference falls to 80s years to 0.1 sec mostly because of travel time decrease in winter. This trend is confirmed by calculation of collective arrivals time change. For winter conditions statistically weighted travel time falls faster then for summer conditions. The trend in signal duration, which was defined through cumulative sum procedure, shows some reduction in signal duration more emphasize in winter then in summer. Cumulative sum procedure in sensitive for vertical temperature gradient, therefore one could conclude the temperature grows in shallow water layer of the ocean. Really the signal duration is defined as a difference in time between the slowest arrivals, which propagate in subsurface waveguide and the fastest deep water arrivals.

Figure 5.7 Travel time variation cross the Fram Strait through the decades from 50s to 80s years. a) – time propagation change along the ray stable through the decades and seasons; b) – collective arrivals time change in seconds; c) – cumulative sum change in seconds. Shaded areas show the values calculated for interpolated data, solid lines correspond to least square regressions.

5.6 Conclusion

Two approaches are considered in the modeling. One of them is based on the stable arrivals selection and determination of travel time variation. The second one consists of defining the trend in the whole signal-arrival spectrum caused by the temperature changes, and computing average parameters of the arriving signal ensemble.

The arrival time fluctuations were investigated for changing oceanographic data. Environmental data variation was provided by shifting the entire sound-speed pattern horizontally with respect to the transmitter-bottom-receiver configuration for a distance essentially more the scale of ocean turbulence spatial correlation. For the isotropic ocean turbulence in each horizontal plane, when the spatial scale of correlation of random oceanographic inhomogeneities is the same in any direction in the horizontal plane, we obtain the rms travel time fluctuations for the 5s arrival close to 30 ms. This value is noticeably larger than signal fluctuations due to surface scattering and ice cover influence. The temperature influence on the stable arrivals was estimated as a gradient of 29 ms/°C for 4s arrival and 37 ms/°C for 5s arrival.

In the course of implementing the second approach there were obtained the collective sum of signal arrivals. The temperature dependence of the arrival-pattern duration leads to variation of the slope of the cumulative sum regression line. The advantage of this approach is that it is based only on relative measurements of arrivals. Measurement of the regression line slope does not require as sophisticated an apparatus to match the receiver and the source clock as it required for travel time measurements. The cumulative time procedure presents the possibility of determining the average temperature along the acoustic path in the ocean without considering detail arrival features. Statistical approach applied for travel time calculation for the signal propagated cross the Fram Strait through the decades reveals some trends, which could be related with temperature change in upper layer of the ocean mostly in winter environment conditions.

Cumulative sum (CUMSUM) and Collective Arrivals Time (CAT) as statistical methods have been considered to find the temperature dependence on acoustical propagation in cross section of Fram Strait. CUMSUM method sensitive to the temperature variation in depth (baroclinic dependence), whereas CAT changes mostly at barotropic temperature effect. 0.1°C per a year or 0.06°C per a decade sensitivity can be reached under the permanent seasonal acoustical monitoring of temperature in Fram Strait.

5.7 References

1. O. M. Johannessen, E. Bjargo, and M. W. Milas, "Global warming and the Arctic", *Science* 271 January p. 129, (1996).
2. J.F. Lynch, H.X. Wu, R. Pawlowicz, P. Worcester, R.E. Keenan, H.C. Graber, O.M. Johannessen, P. Wadhams, R.A. Shuchman. "Ambient noise measurements in the 200-300Hz band from the Greenland Sea tomography experiment" *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **94**(2), p p 1015 (1993)
3. G. Jin, J. F. Lynch, R. Pawlowicz and P. Worcester "Acoustic scattering losses in the Greenland Sea marginal ice zone during the 1988--89 tomography experiment." *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **96** (5), Pt.1, 3045 –3053 (1994).
4. Knud Simonsen and Peter M. Haugen "Heat budgets of the Arctic Mediterranean and sea surface heat flux parameterizations for the Nordic Seas". *J. Geophys. Res.* **101**, No.C3, p.p. 6553-6576 (1996).

5. W. Munk, P. Worcester and C. Wunsch. Ocean Acoustic Tomography.(Cambridge University Press, 1995)
6. O.M. Johannessen, J.A. Johannessen, E. Svendsen, R.A. Schuchman, W.J. Campbell, and E. Josberger "Ice-Edge Eddies in the Fram Strait Marginal Ice Zone ". *Science*, **236**, p.p. 427-429 (1987).
7. K. Naugolnykh, O. Johannessen, I. Esipov, O. Ovchinnikov, Yu. Tuzhilkin, and V. Zosimov, "Numerical simulation of remote acoustic sensing of ocean temperature in the Fram Strait environment," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **104** (2) Pt. 1, pp. 738-746, (1998).
8. E.C. Shang, Y.Y. Wang, and K. Naugolnykh, "Numerical simulation on acoustic propagation in a complex environment -Fram Strait," *Proceedings of the 3rd European Conference on Underwater Acoustics, Heraklion, Greece 1*, pp. 432-439 (1996).
9. J.J. Kagan and L. Knopoff. "Stochastic synthesis of earthquake catalog", *J. Geophys. Res.* **86**, p.p. 2853-2862.J
10. .L. Spiesberger, P.J. Bushong, K. Metzger and T.G. Birdsall, "Ocean acoustic tomography: Estimating the acoustic travel-time with phase." *IEEE J. Oceanic Eng.* **14**, 108-119, (1989).
11. Joint U.S. Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean. NSIDC/CIRES
12. S. Clifford and D. Farmer, "Ocean flow measurement using acoustical scintillation," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **74**(6), 1826-1832 (1983).
13. D. M. Farmer and S. F. Clifford, "Space-Time Acoustic Scintillation Analysis: A New Technique for Probing Ocean Flows," *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering* **OE-11** (1), 42-50 (1986).
14. D.M. Farmer and G.B. Crawford, "Remote sensing of ocean flows by spatial filtering of acoustic scintillations: Observations", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **90**(3), 1582-1591 (1991).
15. R.W. Lee and A.T. Waterman, Jr., "Space Correlations of 35-GHz Transmissions Over a 28-km Path," *Radio Science* **3**(2), 135-139 (1968).
16. R. Esswein and S. Flatte, "Calculation of the phase-structure function density from oceanic internal waves," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **70**(5), 1387-1396 (1981).
17. Naugolnykh, K. A., Esipov, I. B , Ovchinnikov, O. B., Tuzhilkin, Yu. I., Johannessen, O. M. "Sound signal scintillation approach to acoustic monitoring of heat and mass transport through the Fram Strait." 2d Convent of the EAA: Forum Acusticum 99, Berlin, Germany, March 1999.
18. I. Fuks, "Correlation of the fluctuations of frequency spaced signals in a randomly inhomogeneous medium," *Radiotekhn. and Electronic* **3**, 515-524 (1975) (in Russian).
19. V. Tatarskii, "The effect of the turbulent atmosphere on wave propagation." Israel Program for Scientific Translation: Jerusalem, Israel, 1971.
20. C. Garret and W. Munk, "Space-time scales of internal waves: A progress report," *J. Geophys. Res.* **80**, 291-297 (1975).
21. Y. Desaubies, "On the scattering of sound by internal waves in the ocean," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **64**(5), 1460-1468 (1978).
22. I. Fuks, K. Naugolnykh and M. Charnotskii, "Multi-frequency scintillation method for ocean flow measurement," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **106**(2), 2119 (1999).

5.8 Deliverables/Publications

1. Naugolnykh, K. A., Johannessen, O. M., Esipov, I. B., Ovchinnikov, O. B., Tuzhilkin, Yu. I., and Zosimov, V.V., Numerical simulation of remote acoustic sensing of ocean temperature in the Fram Strait environment. *J. Acous. Soc. Am.*, (1998:) **104**(2), pp. 738-746.
2. Naugolnykh, K.A., Shang E.C., and Wang Y.Y. , Esipov, I.B., and Johannessen, O.M.,1998: "Numerical Simulation of the Parametrical Array Application for Ocean Monitoring in the Fram Strait Environment», *Acoustical Physics*. 1999, **45**(4), pp. 448-454
3. Naugolnykh, K., E.C. Shang and Wang, Y.Y. ,1997: "Numerical simulation of the Parametrical Array Application for the Fram Strait Acoustic Monitoring», *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **102**(5), Pt 2, p 3081.
4. Naugolnykh, K., Shang, E.C. and Wang, Y.Y. ,1998: "Arrival Times (Ray/Mode) Treatment for Remote Sensing in a Complex Propagation Environment”, *National Radio Science Meeting, Jan.5-8 1998, Boulder CO, Sec 3 Remote Sensing of the Oceans*, p 145.
5. Naugolnykh, K.A.,Wang, Y.Y., and Shang, E.C., 1998:»Numerical Simulation of the Transverse Current Monitoring in the Fram Strait», *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **104**(3), Pt 2, p.1748.
6. E.C. Shang Y.Y. Wang and K. Naugolnykh, 1996, "Numerical simulation on acoustic propagation in a complex environment - the Fram Strait," *3rd European Conference on Underwater Acoustics, Heraclion, Crete, Greece, 24 -28 June*, p 165-170.
7. .J. Fuks, K.Naugolnykh and M. Charnotskii, 1999:"Multi-frequency scintillation method for ocean flow measurement", *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 106 (4) 2119.
8. Naugolnykh, K. A., Esipov, I. B , Ovchinnikov, O. B., Tuzhilkin, Yu. I., Johannessen, O. M. "Sound signal scintillation approach to acoustic monitoring of heat and mass transport through the Fram Strait." *2d Convent of the EAA: Forum Acusticum 99, Berlin, Germany, March 1999*.
9. K.Naugolnykh, J. Fuks, and M. Charnotskii, 2000:."Multi-frequency scintillation method of ocean flow measurement", *Proc. Fifth European Conf. On Underwater Acoustics, ECUA 2000, Ed. M. Zakharia, Co-editors: P. Chevret, P. Dubail, Lyon, France*, 133-137
10. Esipov, I. B., Naugolnykh, K. A., Johannessen, O. M., Ovchinnikov, O. B., Tuzhilkin, Yu. I., "Sound signal scintillation approach to remote monitoring of heat and mass transport in the Fram Strait," 2000, *Proc. Fifth European Conf. On Underwater Acoustics, ECUA 2000, Ed. M. Zakharia, Co-editors: P. Chevret, P. Dubail, Lyon, France*, 171-176.
11. O. M. Johannessen, H. Sagen, S. Sandven, H. Hobak, K. Hasselman, E. Maier-Reimer, U. Mikolajewicz, zzv. Zsoldatov, L. Bobylev, E. Evert, P. Wadhams, A. Kaletzky, I.B., Esipov, K. A Naugolnykh, "Acoustic monitoring of ocean climate in the Arctic (AMOC)," 2000, *Proc. Fifth European Conf. On Underwater Acoustics, ECUA 2000, Ed. M. Zakharia, Co-editors: P. Chevret, P. Dubail, Lyon, France*, 1297-1303.
12. Naugolnykh, K., Shang, E.C. and Wang, Y.Y. "Acoustic sensing of temperature changes in a strong range-dependent ocean," 2000, *Inverse Problem*, Bristol, UK, (accepted for publication).

6. Sensitivity study of acoustic propagation to current velocity changes using signal scintillation approaches (Subtask 4.3)

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by Russian subcontractors.

6.1 Introduction

Different features of acoustic signals such as ray travel time, amplitude, angle of ray arrival, mode group velocity, and carrier phase are integral functional of the oceanic sound speed and currents fields. The variation of sound signal parameters can be used to solve the inverse problem of the sound speed field and current velocity acoustic measurements [5]. Longitudinal current component can be estimated from differential travel time measurements.

Another possible acoustic scheme would measure currents transverse to the acoustic path by using the correlation of acoustic scintillations recorded at transversely spaced receivers -- a technique that has been suggested for ocean current measurements [12-14], and was based on the pioneer work [15], where such kind of micro wave scintillation transport in a turbulent atmosphere was discovered experimentally. The essence of the technique lies in the interpretation of the combined spatial and temporal variability of forward propagated sound. Sound signal passing through the ocean fine structure is modulated, producing an irregular pattern of amplitude and travel time variations at the receivers. These variations evolve as the intervening medium changes. Under assumption that the fluctuations in the medium are produced mainly by the advection of a frozen fine structure field (Taylor's model of turbulence), evolution of the signal pattern can be directly linked to the motion of the medium. This allows determination of transverse component of the current by measurements of the time lag between the signal variations at two closely spaced receivers. In general, the coherence of sound received by different hydrophones (separated in space, time or frequency) in the ocean is a useful measure of the behavior of the intervening fluid medium [16].

6.2 Computer modeling of the 3D environment

For the modeling of sound signal propagation through the number of mesoscale inhomogeneities it is necessary to simulate 3D inhomogeneity structure with definite parameters. Inhomogeneity movement in our case is regarded in frame of 'frozen turbulence' model, when the environment structure is shifted with the velocity with respect to regarded profile in the space. Taking in the mind vector type of relation between $\delta c(\Gamma_i)$ and water flow velocity one can exclude the temperature dependence for the sound speed by $\delta\tau_i$ measurement for the signals propagated on 16 paths network between the transducers of 4x4 tomography array. The main reason for the precise $\delta\tau_i$ calculation is the sound ray structure changing for the paths.

Computer modeling is based on the original data of $c(z)$ profiles of the Fram Strait environment. Regarded environment is characterized by minimum value of $c(z)$ at the sea surface (subsurface sound waveguide) what is typical for polar ocean. In the east part of the path there is one more minimum $c(z)$ at the depth of 600 m. It corresponds to the warm water income from the Atlantic. In the eastern part of the strait the cold and less salt Arctic water doesn't penetrate at the large depths and flows in subsurface layer. The second $c(z)$ minimum vanish there.

The sound source and the receiver should be placed in these conditions at the depths of 500 m

in order. Rays from the shallower source will be propagating mostly in the subsurface waveguide through the number of inhomogeneity. They can strongly affect the rays so they change their structure (a number of refraction from sea surface). This makes the signal propagation process more comprehensive for the problem regarded. For the deeper source situation the length of the ray cycle increases and the number of ray incomes to perturbed subsurface layer is decreases at the strait width. Beside this the deeper rays can touch the bottom and scatters there. Hence the sea depth at the place of source and the receiver situation is needed sufficiently large for $c(z)$ at the bottom increases the same value in the inhomogeneity at the subsurface layer. Taking this consideration in mind we regard the pathway in the eastern part of the Fram Strait. Sound source is placed at the depth of 500 m at the distance of 60 km from Prince Karl Land coast. The receivers are placed at the distance of 250 km to the west from the source at the depths 100, 200 and 300 m respectively. Calculations revile the stable rays presence in this configuration source-receiver. This rays have four or five touching of the sea surface at the different environment variation.

As it was already mentioned the environment conditions at the eastern and the western parts of the pathway are different. West-Spitzbergen current dominated at the beginning of the pathway changes to the East-Greenland current. They have a constant configuration and therefore we cannot regard them as a random inhomogeneity. As for inhomogeneities we will presume them as a deviations from the regular dependence $c_0(z, r)$ where z - is a depth and r is a distance from the source. Here it was calculated a $c_0(z, r)$ regression on each horizon z_j . This regression dependence is defined by least square method. Therefore for inhomogeneity we presume the sound speed variation, $\delta c_0(z_j, r) = c(z_j, r) - c_0(z_j, r)$ which describe the spatial sound speed fluctuation at the z_j horizon with respect to initial $c(z_j, r)$ dependence. In process of computer simulation of $\delta c_k(z_j, r)$ the spatial spectrum of inhomogeneity and their variation are regarded. Initial value of inhomogeneity variation Δ^2 at the z_j horizon is calculated from $\delta c_0(z_j, r)$ realization. To generate another realization $\delta c_1(z_j, r)$ in each point (z_j, r) we add a random value from interval $\{-0.1\Delta \div +0.1\Delta\}$ with appropriate sign, which corresponds to derivative sign of initial function $\delta c_0(z_j, r)$. It is needed to maintain the relation between the generated realization and the initial one. Appropriate algorithm can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} [\delta c_k(z_j, r_i) - \delta c_{k-1}(z_j, r_i)] \times [\delta c_{k-1}(z_j, r_{i+1}) - \delta c_{k-1}(z_j, r_i)] &\geq 0 \\ [\delta c_k(z_j, r_i) - \delta c_k(z_{j-1}, r_i)] \times [\delta c_{k-1}(z_j, r_i) - \delta c_{k-1}(z_{j-1}, r_i)] &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To fit spatial property of generated realizations they weighted on initial power spectrum and passes through the Hamming window to avoid the edge effect. Power spectrum of generated realization can be corrected with respect to initial field of the inhomogeneity. To preserve the value of the δc fluctuation we normalize the variance of δc by the factor of Δ_0 / Δ where Δ is variance of δc . Data on 12000 environment realizations for were generated in the process of computer simulation. Examples of spatial spectra (or periodograms) of the simulated environment variation are shown at Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1 Spatial spectra (or periodograms) of the simulated sound speed variations. Curves 2,3,4,5 corresponds 40h, 280 h , 560 h and 700 h time delay for the environment velocity drift $u = 0.9 \text{ km/h}$.

6.3 Signal scintillation approach

Signal scintillation approach developed for the regular medium with the straightforward signal propagation could be extended to the inhomogeneous ocean waveguide, where signal propagates along the trajectory, which oscillates many times. Previously, some estimates for sensitivity of acoustical monitoring across the Fram Strait were made using both rays [17] and normal mode approaches [8]. Acoustic signal propagation through the varying environment is computer simulated with respect to broad frequency band sounding of Fram Strait environment. The distance between signal source and receivers is regarded 250 km to overlap the main currents in the Fram Strait trough. Each acoustic signal travels to the receiver along many different paths with different travel times because of the channel sound propagation condition. Beside this the travel time changes with respect to varying environment what makes it possible to follow the changing environment in time or another words to follow the velocity of the environment movement in the "frozen" environment approximation. It was shown [7] the possibility to find some stable eigen rays configuration for the acoustical monitoring of the Fram Strait, which doesn't change under the environment perturbation, typical for Fram Strait. Such stable eigen rays pass mainly in quiet deep water with seldom penetration to the inhomogeneous upper ocean layers. They touch the surface only 4 or 5 times at the width of Fram Strait (250-300 km). Therefore they have very coarse accuracy for the spatial resolution.

Let's regard the problem to use the total signal arrivals for the acoustical monitoring of the Fram Strait cross section. Travel time variation for the multiple arrivals we define statistically by the method of maximum likelihood [10]. Example of signal arrivals at two adjacent environment realizations is shown at Figure 6.2. Travel time variations are computed there from the cross-correlation of such random arrivals. This procedure makes it possible to follow the collective time of arrivals with respect of variable environment. Signal arrivals were normalized to 1 with respect to their amplitudes in our approach. Example at the Figure 6.2(c) shows an increment in time propagation of 0.6 ms for the regarded adjacent environment realizations. For the modeling of sound signal propagation in variable structure of 3D inhomogeneity structure with definite parameters was simulated. Inhomogeneity movement is simulated in frame of 'frozen turbulence' model, when the environment structure is shifted with the velocity corresponding to profile regarded. Taking in the mind vector type of relation between sound speed value and water flow velocity one can exclude the temperature

dependence for the travel time by reciprocal propagation of the signals. The sound sources and the receivers are placed in our model at the depths of 500 m to let the eigen rays to overlap the main ocean layers with specific features of the currents. Rays from the shallower source will be propagating mostly in the subsurface waveguide through the number of inhomogeneity. They can strongly affect the rays so they change their structure (number of surface touching). This makes the signal propagation process more comprehensive for the problem regarded. For the deeper source situation the length of the ray cycle increases and the number of ray incomes to perturbed subsurface layer is decreases at the strait width. Previous estimations show the travel time variation in order of 10 ms in Fram Strait cross section [7]. To resolve this value we regard the signal frequency bandwidth of 1 kHz in our calculations, what corresponds to signal duration of 1 ms.

Figure 6.2 Two adjacent sets of signal arrivals separated of 20 min of environment shift (a,b), ordinates show the value of signal dampening with respect to the level at 1 km distance from the source; c - appropriate cross-correlation function for normalized arrivals shown at (a,b).

Signal travel time variation obtains in collective time arrival procedure as a result of sum up of successful series of travel time increments calculated as time shift of cross-correlation maximum of the signal arrivals for adjacent environment realizations. An example of travel time variation for the signal propagated through simulated environment is shown at Figure 6.3. The fact of travel time fluctuations are proved to be co-related for the signals crossed the stream along the paths at small angles with respect each other, makes it possible to consider the registration of their fluctuations by means of underwater array.

Let's regard the symmetrical tomography array consists from four equally spaced sources and four receivers (Figure 6.4). The simulation has been done for the space between the array elements both the sources and the receivers is equal $a = 5$ km. Therefore the full aperture both transmitter and receiver part of array is much less in the dimension with respect to range of sounding environment. Thus one could say there on 'Small Aperture Tomography Scheme'. Network from 16 paths, which covers the area between the sources and the receivers, cross each other at small angles is regarded there. Inhomogeneities of the medium while they are flowing

through the area covered this network will affect the travel time for the signals, propagated along each of these paths. Travel time fluctuations of the signals propagated along the different paths will be retarded each other at different times in frame of 'frozen turbulence' model. This time lag is defined as function of velocity of inhomogeneity flow u and the distance of it movement trajectory from the base of sources r or the distance from the receivers $l-r$. Here l is the distance between the array bases. From simple geometrical considerations one can determine these time lags as it is shown at the Table 6.1. The first figure of the index there means the number of the source, and the second one corresponds to the receiver position.

Figure 6.3 Travel time variation of the signal crossed the simulated moving environment.

Figure 6.4 Scheme of tomography array.

Table 6.1 Time lags for correlated fluctuations.

$t_{44} = 0$	$t_{34} = \frac{a(l-r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{24} = \frac{2a(l-r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{14} = \frac{3a(l-r)}{u_0 l}$
$t_{43} = \frac{ar}{u_0 l}$	$t_{33} = \frac{a}{u_0}$	$t_{23} = \frac{a(2l-r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{13} = \frac{a(3l-2r)}{u_0 l}$
$t_{42} = \frac{2ar}{u_0 l}$	$t_{32} = \frac{a(l+r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{22} = \frac{2a}{u_0}$	$t_{12} = \frac{a(3l-r)}{u_0 l}$
$t_{41} = \frac{3ar}{u_0 l}$	$t_{31} = \frac{a(l+2r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{21} = \frac{a(2l+r)}{u_0 l}$	$t_{11} = \frac{3a}{u_0}$

Summing up the travel time fluctuations for the signals passed along the different paths with appropriate time lags leads to the rise of the correlated fluctuations with respect to number of signal realizations N (that is in 16 times), whereas the other fluctuations in process of random summation will be increased only in proportion of $N^{1/2}$ (or in 4 times in our case). It worth to take into consideration that such a summation has any sense only for signal fluctuations, which are conditioned by the fine structure of the hydrographic inhomogeneities with a spatial scale less or in order of the space between the array elements. The larger structure, spatial scale of which is more then the dimension of the array base will simultaneously influence the signals passed along the whole network of the paths. Therefore there are no any sufficient phase shift in travel time fluctuations caused by the large-scale inhomogeneities. They affect simultaneously all signals propagated along any path of the array. For this reason low frequency fluctuations were rejected passing the signals through the filter, frequency band of which is defined by the transfer of the inhomogeneity which scale is in the range of 4 - 7km. This range is conditioned by the mentioned above the array dimension and is related with the boundary of 'frozen turbulence' model application. It is known this model is valid for the medium transfer at the range of 3-4 eddy spatial scale. At the larger distance the eddy shape changes and loses the relation with its original form. Another words the medium perturbation is proved to be non correlated. Thus the spatial scale of 4 km seems to be the highest limit in the spectrum for the inhomogeneities which can be regarded in the frame of 'frozen turbulence' model at the array aperture of 15km.

Example of the current profile retrieval with respect to this procedure is shown on Figure 6.5. Positive values correspond to North direction (West Spitsbergen Current) and the negative ones correspond to opposite direction (East Greenland Current). Shadowed areas show the value of variation of the signals sum in percent from maximum for properly delayed travel time propagation along 16 paths of array network in accord with the rule put at the Table 6.1 (relative value of array tuning). Spatial resolution of the retrieval is defined by the accuracy of 3D environment simulation.

Figure 6.5 Example of water current retrieval. Solid line shows the initial current profile, shadowed areas show the relative value of array tuning in accord with the rule put at the Table 6.1.

6.4 Multi-frequency scintillation method for transverse ocean current measurement

The transverse flow of inhomogeneous fluid produces fluctuation of the acoustic signal passing through it. These fluctuations vary with the CW signal frequency change due to variation of the Fresnel zone size and diffraction angles. Respectively, the fluctuations of amplitude and phase of frequency-spaced signals are coherent at the low frequency and noncoherent at the high-frequency band. The frequency cutoff of the coherence function depends upon the flow velocity at given fine structure of the flow. The measurement of the cutoff frequency allows to determine the transverse current velocity [18]. This method can be considered as the “frequency-domain” version of the conventional scintillation approach to the current velocity registration based on the measurement of the signal correlation transmitted from the source to the two separated in space receivers (space-domain scintillation) [12]. Consider the propagation through the random medium of the two CW waves of different frequencies $\omega_{1,2}$:

$$\varphi_{1,2} = \exp(\psi_{1,2}(t) - i\omega_{1,2}t), \quad (8)$$

φ is the velocity potential, $\psi_{1,2}$ is the complex phase, $\psi_{1,2}(t) = \chi_{1,2}(t) + iS_{1,2}(t)$, $\chi_{1,2}$ and $S_{1,2}$ are the log-amplitude and the phase of the signal respectively. In the framework of the smooth perturbation method the fluctuation of the complex phase of the signal at the distance L from the source is [19]:

$$\psi_n(t) = \frac{k_{1,2}^2 L^L}{2\pi} \frac{dx}{x(L-x)} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy dz \mu(x, y, z, t) \exp\left\{ \frac{ik_{1,2}(y^2 + z^2)L}{2x(L-x)} \right\}, \quad (9)$$

here $k_{1,2} = \omega/c$ is acoustical wave number, c is the sound velocity, $\mu(x, y, z, t)$ is the refraction index fluctuation. It is supposed that the sound waves are propagating along the x-axis. The relative coherence of the signals can be characterized by the reciprocal correlation function and its Fourier transform - the reciprocal spectrum. The reciprocal spectrum of the log-amplitude fluctuation is:

$$W_x^{1,2}(\nu) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp(i\nu\tau) \langle \chi_n(t) \chi_m(t + \tau) \rangle d\tau \quad (10)$$

It depends upon the spectrum of the inhomogeneities in the medium that can be characterized by the spatial power spectrum density of the refractive index fluctuations

$$\Phi_\mu(\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_z) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^3} \int B_\mu(x, y, z) \exp[-i(\kappa_x x + \kappa_y y + \kappa_z z)] dx dy dz, \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where } B_\mu(x, y, z) = \langle \mu(X, Y, Z) \mu(X + x, Y + y, Z + z) \rangle \quad (12)$$

and can be expressed as follows:

$$W_x^{1,2}(\nu) = \frac{\pi k^2 L}{1 - \Omega^2} \int_0^L dx \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\kappa_y d\kappa_z \Phi_\mu(0, \kappa_y, \kappa_z) \times \delta[\nu - \Omega_l(\kappa_y, \kappa_z)] \left\{ \cos\left[x(L-x) \frac{\kappa^2}{kL} \Omega \right] - \cos\left[x(L-x) \frac{\kappa^2}{kL} \right] \right\}. \quad (13)$$

Here Ω is the relative frequency spacing and k is the median sound wave number:

$$\Omega = \frac{\omega_2 - \omega_1}{\omega_2 + \omega_1}, \quad k = \frac{2k_1k_2}{k_1 + k_2},$$

while the $\Omega_L(\kappa_y, \kappa_z)$ is the dispersion equation of the inhomogeneities, κ_y and κ_z are the horizontal and vertical wave numbers of the internal waves. At the frequency range corresponding to ocean sensing experiments the refraction index fluctuation is dominated by the internal waves with a particular empirical spectrum suggested by Gurrett and Munk [20]. The space-time version of the Gurrett-Munk spectrum of the internal that can be taken in the form presented by Desaubies [21]

$$\Phi_\mu(\kappa_z, \nu) = \frac{8}{\pi^2} \langle \mu^2 \rangle \omega_i \frac{\beta_*(\nu^2 - \omega_i^2)^{1/2}}{\nu^3 (\beta_*^2 + \kappa_z^2)}, \quad (14)$$

$\beta_*^2 = t^2 (N^2 - \nu^2)$, $t=1-2$ cpm/Hz, ν is the frequency of oscillation, N , ω_i are the buoyancy and inertial frequency, μ^2 is the mean square index of refraction. The dispersion relation of the internal waves in the presence of current of velocity U moving along the y axis is:

$$\Omega_L(\kappa_y, \kappa_z) = \left[\frac{N^2 \kappa_y^2 + \omega_i^2 \kappa_z^2}{\kappa_y^2 + \kappa_z^2} \right]^{1/2} + U \kappa_y. \quad (15)$$

To demonstrate the main features of the approach we present below the equations for the case when the second term in the Eq. (15) dominates, i.e. the internal wave field can be considered as frozen advected by the current of velocity U . Then the results of the numerical modeling of the general case when the internal wave propagation is taken into account, will be presented. The reciprocal spectrum can be expressed in terms of dimensionless function $Z(f, \Omega)$:

$$W_\chi^{(1,2)}(\nu) = \frac{\pi k^{3/2}}{(1 - \Omega^2)f} [Z(f, \Omega) - Z(f, 1)], \quad (16)$$

$$\text{where } Z(f, \Omega) = \int_0^1 d\xi \int_0^\infty \frac{d\eta \cos[\xi(1-\xi)(1+\eta)f^2\Omega]}{(1+\varepsilon^2\eta)^2[(1+\eta)f^2 + p^2(1-\varepsilon^2)]}$$

and $f = \nu/\nu_0$, $\varepsilon = \omega_i/N$, $\xi = x/L$, $p = Nt(L/k)^{1/2}$, $\eta = \kappa_z^2(L/k)/f^2$. The characteristic frequency ν_0 being the frequency of intersection by the flow inhomogeneities the Fresnel zone of the sound signal of wave k

$$\nu_0 = U(k/L)^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

is the important parameter of the process. Normalized reciprocal spectrum is:

$$\Gamma_\chi^{(1,2)}(f) = \frac{W_\chi^{(1,2)}(f)}{[W_\chi^{(1,1)}(f)W_\chi^{(2,2)}(f)]^{1/2}}, \quad (18)$$

The oscillation of the normalized spectrum $\Gamma_\chi^{(1,2)}$ is determined by the term $\cos[\xi(1-\xi)(1+\eta)f^2\Omega]$, its contribution becomes essential under the condition [22]: $f^2\Omega \approx 1$

This conclusion is supported by the numerical evaluation of the reciprocal spectrum derived for the general case when both the internal wave evolution and the current are taken into account. The normalized reciprocal spectrum of the frequency-spaced sound signals propagation through the flow perturbed by the internal waves as a function of normalized frequency $f = \nu/\nu_0$ is presented in the Figure 6.6. It is seen that the point of the x -axis cross-section ν grows up with

the increasing of the current velocity U and the oscillation in the reciprocal spectrum of frequency-spaced signals occurs at the frequency

$$v_c \approx v_0 \sqrt{\frac{L}{k\Omega}} = \frac{U}{\sqrt{\Omega}}, \quad (19)$$

that is in proportion to the current velocity U . By measurement of the frequency of oscillation the current velocity can be determined

$$U = v_c \sqrt{k\Omega}. \quad (20)$$

Consider, for example, the transverse current \ probing at a distance of $L=2$ km. Let the current velocity be $U = 10$ cm/s. The appropriate sound wave frequency is $\omega/2\pi = 3 \cdot 10^4$ Hz, so $k=125$ m^{-1} . Then $v_0 = U(k/L)^{1/2} = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ Hz and the frequency cutoff $v_c = 2.7 v_0/\Omega^{1/2} = 2.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ Hz for $\Omega=0.1$. The Brunt-Vaisala frequency N is of the order of $10^{-3} - 10^{-4}$ Hz; therefore the relative accuracy of the current velocity estimation due to the internal wave movement is $\Delta U/U \approx 10^{-2}$.

Thus, transverse flow of inhomogeneous fluid produces fluctuations of the acoustic signal passing through it. These fluctuations vary with the CW signal frequency change due to variation of the Fresnel zone size and diffraction angles. Respectively, the fluctuations of amplitude and phase of frequency-spaced signals are coherent at the low fluctuation frequency and non-coherent at the high-frequency band. The coherence function behavior depends upon the flow velocity at the given fine structure of the flow. The measurement of the cut off frequency allows determination of the transverse current velocity. The application of the multi-frequency signal allows, in addition to the current velocity, estimation of the fine structure parameters.

Figure 6.6 The coherence function of log-amplitude fluctuations of CW signal, with the different frequency separation Ω , propagating through the media perturbed by internal waves with Gurret-Munk spatial power spectrum ($\varepsilon=0.04, p=1.7$).

6.5 Summary and discussion

Space-time scintillation analysis offers a promising method of remote acoustic sensing of current in ocean. The evolution of the scintillation pattern is related to the advection of the inhomogeneous medium through the sound beam, thus providing a basis for flow velocity measurement. Previously this method was developed and realized at small distances in the ocean where the waveguide propagation doesn't occur. Space-time correlation technique is applied to a model of the transverse current measurement at large ocean scale in the Fram Strait environment where waveguide sound signal propagation takes place. Variable environment leads to change of the sound signal structure due to variation of ray configuration. Conventional space-time scintillation analysis is not applicable in this case. However, even in a complex environment, it is possible to find some stable characteristics of the sound signal that can be used for the inverse problem solution. One of them is the so-called stable ray, which conserves its configuration in variable environment. It is shown that the stable rays can exist in the deep water part of the cross section of the Fram Strait. They penetrate to the depth of more than 2000 m and propagate mostly in deep water layers in quiet medium with seldom exits to the perturbed upper layer. The deep rays provide the fastest arrivals of the sound signal. Stable configuration of the fastest arrivals allows researchers to use space-time scintillation analyses to the travel time variation to retrieve the spatial current velocity profile. A 3D ocean model was constructed on the basis of the experimental data on the sound speed profiles. Computer modeling of the sound signal propagation in the Fram Strait was performed to obtain the travel time variation due to inhomogeneous medium flow. Space-time correlation analyses of the arrival time fluctuations allows researchers to inverse the current velocity profile.

Estimated accuracy is mostly related to the number of exits of stable rays to the perturbed upper layer that affect the travel-time variations and is proved to be sufficient to resolve the special characteristics of the current velocity distribution.

Other stable characteristics of the sound signal are the collective time and cumulative sum of arrivals. The collective time is in essence the mean arrivals; it indicates the total shift of the arrival pattern. The cumulative sum consists of defining the trend in the signal-arrival spectrum caused by the sound speed profile changes and computing average parameters of the arriving signal ensemble that can be used at the inversion problem consideration.

Signal scintillation approach was developed for analyses of the signal in frequency-time domain. The transverse flow of inhomogeneous fluid produces fluctuations of the acoustic signal passing through it. These fluctuations vary with the CW signal frequency change due to variation of the Fresnel zone size and diffraction angles. Respectively, the fluctuations of amplitude and phase of frequency-spaced signals are coherent at the low fluctuation frequency and non-coherent at the high-frequency band. The coherence function behavior depends upon the flow velocity at the given fine structure of the flow. The measurement of the cut off frequency allows determination of the transverse current velocity. The application of the multi-frequency signal allows, in addition to the current velocity, estimation of the fine structure parameters.

Accuracy the regarded inversion methods is restricted by "frozen turbulence" model. Let's suppose two parallel sound pathways crossing the stream and separated at some distance D and regard the process of signal propagation along these paths. Inhomogeneous flow effect on travel time of the signal will be the same but with some time delay t , which related with distance D and flow velocity u , $t = D/u$. 'Frozen turbulence' model can be usually applied for a distance $D \cong 3\langle L \rangle$, where $\langle L \rangle$ is a spatial scale of environment variance. The accuracy of delay time definition for the high signal-to-noise ratio can be $\Delta t \cong 0.3\Delta\tau$, where $\Delta\tau$ is the width of

autocorrelation for the travel time signal variation. This value can be estimated as $\Delta\tau \cong \langle L \rangle / u$. Thus the relative accuracy measurement is $\Delta t / t \cong 0.1$, which leads to estimation for current velocity inversion as $\Delta u / u \cong 0.1$.

Special features of the Fram Strait environment demand specific inversion methods to monitor heat and mass transportation from Atlantic into Arctic basin. Considered method of acoustics remote monitoring by means of sound signal scintillation received by the array of the gages spaced at the distance where current velocity and its direction as well couldn't change essentially (15 km) in considered case) seems suits to environmental conditions in Fram Strait. Appropriate time delay for the signal from the receivers gives us the possibility to adjust the receiving array to the range chosen for the current velocity monitoring. Estimated accuracy is shown to be sufficient to resolve the special features of regarded current spatial profile.

Mind the heavy climate (ice covers the strait most seasons in the year) considered method could be realized by using of autonomous bottom buys with transceivers. Let's discuss the main parameters of such acoustics system. Travel time variation for the signal crossed the Strait is estimated as several of tens of milliseconds at the distance of 200 km. Crucial features for autonomous acoustics apparatus are to resolve arriving signals with accuracy of $\Delta\tau = 1\text{ms}$ on the pathway regarded. Following to [2], choose the central frequency of the signal 250 Hz with the frequency band $\Delta F = 100\text{ Hz}$. Spectral density of sea noise in Arctic is hardly above 70 dB re 1 mPa in frequency band of 1 Hz, that leads to the noise level estimation under the coherent processing in signal duration $\Delta T = 100\text{ s}$ as $NL = 50\text{ dB}$ re 1 mPa. Signal loss SL we estimate as sum of dampening (10^{-2} dB per 1 km or $SL = 2\text{ dB}$ at the chosen frequency at the whole pathway), attenuation loss AL according to spherical law propagation ($AL = 106\text{ dB}$ re source level at 1 m for 200 km path) and ice cover influence (1 dB for each signal reflection [2], or reflection loss estimation is $RL = 5\text{ dB}$ for the ray, which is touching the surface 5 times). Therefore one can estimate the total signal loss at the path of 200 km as $TL = SL + AL + RL = 113\text{ dB}$. Condition for the travel time resolution demands the signal-to-noise ration $SNR = 1/\Delta\tau \Delta F = 10$ or 20 dB. Summing up these considerations we come to the final estimation for the source level at 1 m

$$SL \geq NL + TL + SNR = 183\text{dB}$$

Another word acoustical power of sound source of each transceiver should exceed 16W. Usually they used a vertical chain of the receivers for the resolution of signal arrived on different rays or modes. Therefore signal energy, needed for the environment probing in such a condition could be less in number of the elements in the receiver chain. For 16 receiving elements in the chain it sufficient to use a transmitter with the power of 1W.

Energy ability of the autonomous buy should be estimated from the typical time of arrival signal variation. This time is conditioned by the environment fine structure advection. Spatial dimension of the smallest component of environment structure, which affect travel time variation, we estimated as 4 km. For a typical current velocity less then 1 km per hour we estimate period of signal envelope radiation as $T = 1$ hour or 24 sound pulses per a day. Mind the efficiency of electrical to acoustical conversion (50%) one could estimate the energy needed to transmit sound pulses along 200 km path as 480Whours per a year. This amount is comparable or rather less then energy capacity of conventional car battery.

Summarize the results of the computer simulation of the current velocity inversion by means of 4x4 tomography array in Fram Strait environment condition with the result of energy capacity evaluation for autonomous operation of bottom buy in a year period we come to the conclusion on the principal possibility to realize permanent acoustical monitoring of heat and mass transportation into Arctic through Fram Strait.

6.6 Conclusion

Signal scintillation approach was developed to retrieve current profile in Fram Strait cross section in small aperture tomography scheme. Both CAT and Stable Ray approaches have been considered for application of signal scintillation procedure. 10% accuracy can be in inversion procedure for 4×4 array of 15 km aperture for 210 km path. Double frequency signal scintillation method was considered to transverse advection velocity detect. This method can be regarded as a “frequency-domain” version of the scintillation approach based on the measurement of correlation of the signals transmitted from the source to two separated in space receivers and can be developed to realize ‘one path tomography scheme’.

Preliminary estimations of bottom autonomous system has been done for the small aperture tomography scheme in Fram Strait cross section.

6.7 References

References for this chapter is found in Section 5.7.

6.8 Deliverables/Publications

Deliverables/Publications from Russian subcontractors are listed in Section 5.8.

7. Stability of individual rays in the Fram Strait

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by NERSC personnel.

7.1 Abstract

Environmental data for the decades 1950 - 1980, summer and winter seasons, and a detailed mapping of a meso scale eddy, is used with the ray tracing code RAY to study the stability of rays in the Eastern part of the Fram strait. The main conclusion is that some rays are found to be stable enough to be identified most of the time, even during passing eddies. These rays are also found to be penetrating down to 800 - 1000 m, thus representing promising candidates for acoustic thermometry of the West Spitsbergen current.

7.2 Introduction

Acoustic thermometry based on precision measurement of individual eigenray arrival times depends on the possibility to identify a certain number of eigenrays during changing environmental conditions on different time scales: hourly variations due to internal waves, diurnal variations related to tides and changing weather conditions, monthly changes due to passing meso scale vortices, seasonal variations, and changes due to (eventual) global warming. In this study we focus on ray identification during the passage of a mesoscale eddy and on seasonal variations based on mean environmental conditions measured for the decades 1950s through 1980s. The environmental data used is collected for the AMOC project from the Joint US Russian Atlas of the Arctic Ocean, and a trace of "SEASOR" data along the 70°N latitude taken in 1997 by the AOGC expedition, depicting a typical meso scale eddy. For the simulations the code «RAY» by J. Bowling *et al.* was used [1]. In addition the PE-code «RAM» by M. Collins *et al.* [2] was used to find the optimal position of source and receiver.

7.3 Method

From an acoustical point of view the Fram Strait is an extremely difficult environment to monitor because of the two opposite currents which are displaced horizontally: On the eastern side the West Spitsbergen current is leading a warm flux of water northwards, while on the west side the East Greenland current flows southward with cold, lower salinity water from the Arctic basin. Besides, the western half is ice covered most of the year to different degrees, and therefore not easy accessible for deployment of equipment, and especially not with buoys on the surface. In this report we therefore focus on a situation with the source placed almost in the middle of the strait, and a receiver array on the western flank near Svalbard. Figure 1 shows the situation depicting the bathymetry of the Fram Strait, the mean sound speed distribution for the summer 50 decade and the position of source and receiver.

The seasonal variations are seen mostly in the upper water column, down to about 600 m. Because of the surface sound ducts which appear in the upper layers it is necessary to lower the sound source to about 500 m in order to avoid large shadow zones and insonify also the deeper water masses. This is seen in the two examples of runs with the RAM code shown in Figure 2, where the only difference is the sound source depth. Figure 2b also shows a concentration zone near 400 km at depths about 300 m. This helped us in locating a good position for the receiver, at depth 300 m, to be used in RAY simulations for obtaining a large number of eigenrays.

Figure 7.1 Bathymetry of the Fram Strait and mean sound speed distribution in the summers 1950s. The position of sound source and receiver used in the ray tracing is also indicated.

Figure 7.2 (a) Transmission loss by RAM simulation. Source depth 100 m, frequency 100 Hz. (b) Transmission loss by RAM simulation. Source depth 500 m, frequency 100 Hz.

Meso scale eddy data were incorporated into the environmental data in the following way. First, the sound speed data for the eddy was interpolated on a regular grid horizontally and vertically in terms of sound speed differences (with a global mean of zero). The grid cell size was chosen as 1.77 km times 2 m. Second, a *matlab* program "meso_ssp2ray.m" was prepared,

which adds a vertical margin at the bottom and a horizontal margin on each side, with height and width at choice, in which the sound speed difference is tapered using linear interpolation from zero at the outer edge to the full value at the inner edge. Further, this program allows the expanded meso data to be added to the selected decade mean sound speed data at a selected position, measured in km Eastwards from $+10^{\circ}\text{W}$ along the 79°N latitude, starting at the most western point of the meso data. Also, the amplitude of the meso data can be adjusted by a factor of choice, typically 0 - 1.0. During this process the decade mean sound speed data also has to be interpolated both in depth and range to match the meso data grid. The result is saved in terms of two ssp-data files, one for the original data set with the new interpolation, and one with the meso data added. This program exists in two versions, one formatting for RAY, the other for RAM. The standard positions of source and receiver are range 250 km and 410 km, depth 500m and 300m, respectively. In RAM a frequency of 100 Hz was used - this is not relevant in RAY simulations. Matlab codes are presented in Section 0.

7.3.1 Eigenrays

Identification of eigenrays is based on number of top and bottom turns, and direction at source and receiver. This gives each ray a signature like for example «+4 3-», meaning: Starting upwards, 4 top turns, 3 bottom turns, ending downwards (the last sign is redundant but is kept for convenience). In each run the eigenrays are numbered successively, starting with the steepest angle downwards at the source. To simplify the identification of the eigenrays they are also named alphabetically starting with the first in the series of the seasonal data, (i.e. following the ray numbers in the first case) with capital letters. Rays appearing later in the series are named with small letters, and occasionally with greek letters. In some of the figures the same naming convention has been used.

7.3.2 Ray fans

A separate study was made by launching a large number of rays in a narrow window of source angles, and investigating the condition of each ray on the arrival at the source range (410 km) regardless of depth. Only the rays actually reaching this distance was kept. The ensemble of the three parameters: source angle, arrival time and arrival depth represents points on a 3-dimensional curve, the projections of which yields valuable information on the stability of rays. Such plots also help in clarifying differences between rays having the same signature (defined above), but still different properties. In the runs presented here the source position was the same as before (250 km, 500 m). 1000 rays were launched in the interval $+6$ to -6 degrees. Typically 600 - 800 of these reached the receiver range.

7.4 Results

7.4.1 Seasonal data-eigenrays

The number of eigenrays varies between 2 and 14 for the original environmental data sets. Starting with Summer 50, attempts were made to identify eigenrays from season to season, as indicated with capital letters. None of these can be identified in all the runs. Especially Winter 60s is problematic, since only two eigenrays exist, and neither of these matches any in the Summer 50s. Winter 60s' two eigenrays have no matches in any of the summer seasons, but one of them (h) in winter seasons. An additional identification starting from the Winter 50s (small letters) clarifies some of the remaining eigenrays. Table 7.1 shows the details of the eigenrays.

Table 7.1 Details of eigenrays for the different seasons.

Summer 50s Eigenray no.	Arrival time s	Intensity *1e ¹⁰	Source angle degrees	Signature and identity code
1	109.578922	0.930911	-4.000000	-3 4+ A
2	109.521966	0.242292	-1.673788	-3 3- B
3	109.512947	0.182512	-1.406049	-2 3+ C
4	109.542309	0.322999	1.710887	+3 3+ D
5	109.553794	0.177132	2.303030	+4 3- E

Winter 50s				
1	109.804055	0.483513	-2.449291	-4 4- a
2	109.776356	0.183707	-2.109541	-3 4+ b, A
3	109.773906	0.904159	-1.622094	-3 4+ c
4	109.800366	0.054397	-1.571214	-4 4- d
5	109.810851	0.025372	-1.098971	-4 5+ e
6	109.834826	0.059241	-1.087237	-5 5- f
7	109.821645	0.292429	2.787879	+4 4+ g
8	109.854195	0.442941	3.272727	+5 4- h

Summer 60s				
1	109.672186	0.393492	-4.000000	-4 4- a
2	109.646796	0.562066	-3.030303	-3 4+ A
3	109.602504	0.701501	-1.575758	- 3 3- B
4	109.597412	0.329029	-1.002620	- 2 3+ C
5	109.628983	0.362610	1.714429	+ 3 3+ D
6	109.637409	0.685065	2.303030	+ 4 3- E
7	109.700815	0.694232	4.484848	+ 4 4+ g

Winter 60s				
1	109.850465	4.637160	1.333333	+5 4-
2	109.852320	1.474797	3.030303	+5 4- h

Summer 70s				
1	109.678258	0.344352	-3.515152	-4 4- a
2	109.653623	0.430099	-2.926156	-3 4+ A
3	109.610445	2.925430	-1.818182	-3 3- B
4	109.596654	0.162894	-1.333333	-2 3+ C
5	109.593209	0.127882	-0.567356	-2 3+
6	109.601734	0.384544	0.733678	+3 2-
7	109.633264	0.376698	1.662784	+3 3+ D
8	109.649998	0.740362	2.155658	+4 3- E
9	109.706116	0.885243	4.000000	+4 4+ g

Winter 70s				
1	109.797899	0.498893	-2.303030	-4 4-a
2	109.765376	0.134100	-1.871794	-3 4+ A
3	109.795456	0.617029	0.121212	+4 4+
4	109.795576	0.749974	0.606061	+4 4+
5	109.812642	0.441748	2.787879	+4 4+ g
6	109.848409	0.508883	3.396405	+5 4-h

Summer 80s				
1	109.667134	0.546311	-4.000000	-4 4-a
2	109.642203	0.725846	-3.272727	-3 4+ A
3	109.592421	0.054931	-2.303030	-3 3- B
4	109.581788	0.150319	-1.761256	-2 3+ C
5	109.556834	0.041283	1.090909	+2 2+
6	109.573400	0.208613	1.447979	+3 2-
7	109.612777	0.325657	2.060606	+3 3+ D
8	109.630716	0.665061	2.449166	+4 3- E
9	109.699373	0.918395	4.969697	+4 4+ g

Winter 80s				
1	109.773262	0.262002	-2.446462	-4 4- a
2	109.742690	0.241645	-2.160086	-3 4+ A
3	109.712159	0.235221	-1.449908	-3 3- B
4	109.691902	0.114991	-0.971111	-2 3+ C
5	109.660403	0.547802	-0.606061	-2 3+
6	109.660403	0.547802	-0.606061	-2 3+
7	109.685819	0.028660	-0.132330	-2 3+
8	109.682897	0.042504	-0.047504	-2 3+
9	109.681051	0.028290	0.566043	+2 2+
10	109.703303	0.168311	0.638504	+3 2-
11	109.728574	0.358098	1.266948	+3 3+
12	109.754308	2.244756	1.575758	+4 3- E
13	109.789503	0.459044	2.688485	+4 4+ g
14	109.825181	0.466985	3.117825	+5 4- h

7.4.2 Meso data -eigenrays

Typical results are shown for Summer 70s with meso data added; western corner starting at 300 km, margins 10%. The sound speed data (ssp-data) are shown for this case in Figure 7.3(a) without meso data and Figure 7.3(b) with meso data at full magnitude (factor=1). Eigenrays for these two cases are plotted in Figure 7.4. The number of eigenrays changes from 9 to 18. The arrival times and amplitudes of the individual eigenrays are shown for the cases factor= 0, 0.2, 0.5 and 1, in Figure 7.5 - Figure 7.8, respectively. The identified rays are marked with letters. Only 3 arrays can be followed through all cases. Details are shown in Table 7.2. The distortion of these 3 eigenrays with increasing meso data amplitude is presented in Figure 7.9-Figure 7.11.

The arrival time of identified rays as a function of meso data amplitude is presented in Figure 7.12. Note that arrival time tends to increase for all rays (except for ray g between factor 0 and 0.2). It should also be observed that the amplitudes of the eigenrays show a large variation. In a practical situation only the strongest ones will be discriminated from noise, meaning that less than 3 rays will be identified throughout the sequence simulating a meso scale eddy passage.

Table 7.2 Details of eigenrays for 4 different meso data amplitudes.

Ray no	Arrival time s	Intensity *10 ¹⁰	Start angle degrees	Signature and identity code
Fac=0				
1	109.6771	0.1327	-3,47	-4 4- a
2	109.6536	0.3817	-2,97	-3 4+ A
3	109.6089	0.1867	-1,78	-3 3- B
4	109.5980	0.2586	-1,3	-2 3+ C
5	109.5944	0.0660	-0,25	-2 3+ α
6	109.6028	0.5168	0,68	+3 2- β
7	109.6328	0.1650	1,61	+3 3+ D
8	109.6482	0.0686	2,19	+4 3- E
9	109.7098	0.2967	4,15	+4 4+ g
Fac=0.2				
1	109.6838	0.1793	-3,55	-4 4- a
2	109.6567	0.5134	-2,97	-3 4+ A
3	109.6157	0.8802	-1,6	-3 3- B
4	109.6000	0.0141	-1,34	-2 3+ C
5	109.5949	0.0159	-0,27	-2 3+ α
6	109.6104	0.0033	0,11	+3 2-
7	109.5985	0.0030	0,59	+2 2+
8	109.5982	0.0450	0,91	+2 2+
9	109.6105	0.3568	0,96	+3 2- β
10	109.6364	0.2333	0,19	+3 3+ D
11	109.6527	0.0431	2,11	+4 3- E
12	109.7094	0.3391	3,98	+4 4+ g

Fac=1.0: Ray no	Arrival time s	Intensity *10 ¹⁰	Start angle degrees	Signature and identity code
1	109.6928	0.4503	-3,41	-4 4- a
2	109.6687	0.4336	-2,97	-3 4+ A
3	109.6723	0.0209	-2,74	-3 4+
4	109.6694	0.0795	-2,45	-3 4+
5	109.6183	0.0019	-2,06	-2 3+ α
6	109.8382	0.0	-1,18	-21 22+
7	109.7043	0.0037	-1	-18 19+
8	109.7376	0.0030	-0,92	-11 12+
9	109.5757	0.0490	-0,36	-2 3+
10	109.6907	0.0732	-0,14	-7 7-
11	109.7459	0.0062	0,76	+8 8+
12	109.7459	0.0062	0,76	+8 8+
13	109.7473	0.0208	1,02	+8 8+
14	109.7434	0.0035	1,18	+11 11+
15	109.7834	0.0020	1,94	+10 9-
16	109.6875	0.0021	1,98	+5 4-
17	109.7214	0.0273	3,98	+4 4+ g
18	109.7552	0.1174	4,83	+5 4-

7.4.3 Seasonal data -ray fans

Results for all the seasons are presented in Figure 7.13 - Figure 7.20. (a) shows Depth versus Source angle, (b) Arrival time versus Source angle, and (c) Depth vs. Arrival time. In (a) and (c) also a line representing the source depth 300 m is drawn, to make recognition of the eigenrays in the previous study easier to locate (they have also been marked with letters on some of the figures). A different set of plots is obtained by replacing source angle with receive angle. This will become relevant in an experimental situation, but is not so useful in the present analysis. Examples of such plots are shown in Figure 7.21 for the summer 50s, to be compared to Figure 7.13. A special case is presented in Figure 7.22: To examine the situation if there is no range dependence in the sound speed profile, the situation at the source was chosen in Summer 60s, and ray fan plots produced as previously. Compare with Figure 7.15. Figure 7.23 shows ray fans for the group denoted «ST» below, and for the rays which were found to be the most stable.

7.4.4 Meso data - ray fans

In order to examine the changes during a meso scale eddy passage some ray fan runs were made for different seasons. By changing the amplitude factor of the meso data gradually from 0 to 1 we attempt to simulate the passage of an eddy. Typical results are shown in Figure 7.24 and Figure 7.25, for Summer 60s, meso factor 0.2 and 1.0 respectively. In both cases a 10% margin was added to the meso data below and on each side, with linear interpolation, to avoid artefacts due to discontinuities.

7.5 Discussion

7.5.1 Seasonal variations

The seemingly complicated pattern of the eigenrays is clarified by examination of the ray fan plots. If we consider first the plots of Depth vs. Source angle, Figure 7.13-20(a), a careful examination reveals the following pattern. The curves are basically symmetric, although the symmetry is broken in several aspects - conf. Figure 7.22. The central part consist of a region denoted «ST» in some plots, where the ray arrival time is almost the same for all rays. This region is surrounded basically by 4 undulations, but not all 4 are seen in all plots - the most positive one is never seen. Each of these consists of two branches, each running between top and bottom «turning points». Along each branch the signature defined above is basically constant. The intensity of the sound field is indicated by the density of rays, each shown by a circle: the denser the higher intensity. The central undulations are often disturbed/split by fluctuations/discontinuities. These arise when the sound speed profile is range dependent, and they increase in number and influence when meso-data is added. Sometimes, like in Figure 7.13, they make one undulation seem like two narrow ones. (One may wonder if these fluctuations are of fractal nature, but the present material is not sufficient to allow this to be established).

The region marked ST consists strictly of two branches, but that is not important here. Often these rays are among the first to arrive, but this is not always the case, as seen in Figure 7.14. In general the intensity here is high. The depth of this region is not stable, but in most cases lies between 600 and 700 m (Summer 70s: 50 m). Some times it splits in two (or more) distinguishable regions (Winter 70s and 80s). It seems to be relatively stable even with meso data added, but this remains to be studied further. The bundle of rays belonging to this region is shown for Summer 50s in Figure 7.23(a). It is evident that only depths in a narrow slice between 500 and about 850 m are sonified by these rays.

The plots of arrival time versus source angle, Figure 7.13-20(b), show a higher degree of symmetry than the rest. The main information is the location of the «stable» regions - ST.

Turning to the plots of depth versus arrival time - Figure 7.13-20(c), the most striking feature here is that the steepest rays arrive latest. The common situation when there is a sound channel is exactly the opposite. In these plots we see the regular structure of the later arrivals, corresponding to the flanks in Figure 7.13-20(a), and the more caotic first arrivals, apart from ST. Do notice the big difference between summer and winter situations. The summer shape is fairly typical for all decades, while the winter shape varies more. Especially winter 60s is atypical - Figure 7.16. The winter 80s look more like previous summer shapes. Note that the details in these plots are extremely sensitive to small changes in the sound speed profile. If the profile is interpolated on a different grid size changes may be seen especially in the fluctuations. Thus a different run on the same input data prepared for inclusion of meso data reveals that in Figure 7.14(c) there is an arc missing between points marked «c» and «d» - resembling the one between «b» and «a» in the same figure. In Figure 7.14(b) this part corresponds to the step at 1.6 degrees.

The highest intensities are found in the regions ST. Apart from these the intensity high near the «turning points» and on the outer branches. The latter is important, because here the rays penetrate deepest into the water column, typically down to 800-1000 m, as seen in Figure 7.23(b). If these rays can be detected with some degree of certainty they are promising candidates for acoustic thermometry/tomography. It is also important that these rays seem to be influenced little by the fluctuations which disturb the inner undulations.

Examining now the variations from season to season we get the following picture, referring in particular to Figure 7.13-20(a) and the eigenrays at 300 m depth. In summer 50s the two outer undulations are missing. The most negative branch belongs to the third undulation from the center, and does not reach deep enough to yield an eigenray. This is an example that eigenrays does not always come in pairs. Actually more than the 5 eigenrays found should be expected, but their amplitude would be very low. The corresponding winter season has all undulations present on the negative side, but the most negative one is too deep to give any eigenrays. This undulation is only seen in winter data, and always lies deep. The two pairs of inner undulations are much weaker, and for positive source angles does not give eigenrays. The ST region is somewhat more shallow, and is delayed by about .35 s relative to the summer values. Winter 60s is rather exceptional from the other data sets. Only the third positive undulation gives rise to eigenrays, and one of them is disturbed by a loop in the depth curve, resulting in a different signature than one should expect. The other undulations are too deep, and weakly pronounced, except one which represents a very weak intensity, and has not been found by the algorithm in RAY.

The following seasons follow basically the same pattern. The summer 70 results stand out because the ST region for the first time is split into two parts, one of which is very shallow - only about 50 m. The following winter seasons both have split ST regions.

The plots based on the receive angle, an example of which is given in Figure 7.21, look very different, and are somewhat harder to analyze. Their importance lies in the fact that this is the sort of information one may obtain in an experimental situation (except receive angle versus source angle, Figure 7.21(b), for example by using an extended receiving array with many receivers. Note that the density of rays no longer reflects the true intensity of sound. In Figure 7.21(a) the four eigenrays **a**, **A**, **g** and **h** are identified.

7.5.2 Meso scale eddy variations

The number of eigenrays at a certain depth increases as the amplitude factor is increased. This is revealed in the eigenray data in Table 7.2, and in Figure 7.24-25 (note that the figures are for a different decade than the tabular data). The fluctuations mentioned above increase in number, first in the central undulations, and later also move towards the outer ones. Note, however, that the central ST-region remains remarkably stable, both in depth and in arrival time. At small meso amplitudes the change in arrival time is not dramatic, but at full amplitude a large number of rays arrive substantially later than the main group, Figure 7.25(c). However, a closer look at the arrivals of eigenrays of type **a** and **g** at 300 m depth reveal very small changes, as shown in Table 7.3:

Table 7.3 Arrival times (s) of eigenrays a and g with meso amplitude factor, S60.

Eigenray/Factor	0	0.1	0.2	0.5	1,0
a	109,670	109,668	109,669	109,660	109,668
g	109,701	109,703	109,705	109,709	109,715

Ray **a** does not seem to change significantly at all, but might be difficult to detect at factor 0.5 and higher. Ray **g** show a slight systematic increase up to 14 ms. This indicates that even through the passage of a meso scale eddy, it is possible to identify some of the eigenrays, and that their arrival times are not significantly altered by the eddy. However, if the proposition is

to monitor the details of the eddy the possibility seems not so promising.

7.5.3 Thermometry

In order to demonstrate the sensitivity of the acoustic thermometry based on the «stable» rays **a**, **A**, **g** and **h**, for the decades 50s to 80s, their arrival times for both seasons are shown in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4 Arrival times of eigenrays a, A, g and h for all decades and seasons.

Decade/Ray	a	A	g	H
S50s		109,5789		
W50s	109,8040	109,7764	109,8216	109,8542
S60s	109,6722	109,6468	109,7008	
W60s				109,8523
S70s	109,6783	109,6536	109,7061	
W70s	109,7979	109,7340	109,8128	109,8484
S80s	109,6671	109,7427	109,6994	
W80s	109,7732	109,7427	109,7895	109,8252

There is a marked difference between summer and winter arrival times, typically about 100 ms faster in the summer. A rough estimate of the corresponding sound speed increase in summer gives $\Delta c \approx 1.45$ m/s, corresponding to the temperature being 0.32 degrees warmer in summer than winter seasons. The arrival times are plotted for all rays versus decade, separated in summer and winter season in Fig. 26. We see basically the same trend in all the rays: Slightly decreasing arrival times with decade, and more pronounced at later decades. However, the change is very small: Winter rays arrive 31.4 \pm 2 ms earlier in 1980s than in 1950s, corresponding to an increase in sound speed 0.42 \pm 0.03 m/s, or an increase in temperature of 0.09 °C. A more refined analysis taking into account the details of the ray paths, and comparison to the temperature data used in the sound speed profiles, has to be postponed to further studies.

7.6 Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the stability of rays in the Eastern part of the Fram Strait with respect to seasonal environmental variations and passages of meso scale eddies. It is found that although there are large changes during passing seasons and eddies, some of the rays show a remarkable stability, and ought to be recognizable in an experimental situation for more than 50 % of the time. Furthermore, these rays are the deepest going eigenrays, typically down to 0.8 - 1 km, and accordingly map the most important part of the West Spitsbergen current.

In an experimental situation it is advisable to use a vertical receiving array, with receivers covering depths between 200 - 700 m, perhaps arranged in pairs so that the direction of received rays can be established at different depths.

7.7 References

- 1) Jim Bowlin, «Ray program», Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, 1994.

- 2) M.D. Collins, «Range Dependent Acoustic Model, version 1.2, sept. 1998», Naval Research Laboratories, Washington D.C.

7.8 Source code

List of matlab programs and their listings.

meso_ssp2ray.m: Main program. Reads environmental data from «mat» files, interpolates and adds meso data. Interrogates for specification of data set, position, margin and amplitude of meso data.

sspinter.m: Routine for horizontal interpolation of data set, based on «spline».

expfiltr.m: Routine for adding margins around meso data set.

tabinterp.m: Routine for linear extrapolation of data sets.

meso_ssp2ray.m

```
% meso_ssp2ray.m
%# skript for {\aa} generere ssp-filer for ray fra matlab
% Special version for including meso-data
% Needs ssp data in matrix c (depth z, range r), with non existant data
% padded as NaN , to be read from a data file in "mat" format:
% i.e. summer50.mat or so.
% K is number of ranges, L of depths.
% This version especially adopted for Fram-strait on troll!
%H.H.
%Last modified: 5/5-00
clear
load /usr/users/amoc/Halvor/FRAM-MAT/framg2s % reads bathymetry
d=depth;
rr=range;

xii=1; %Note factor for decimation of ranges!!!

clear depth range % bathymetry read and transformed
KK=length(rr);
filin=input('Enter name of ssp data file for input (summer60 ...): ','s');
eval(['load /usr/users/amoc/Halvor/FRAM-MAT/' filin]);% sound speed data
load /usr/users/amoc/Meso/mesosssp2.mat % mesodata
% Here begins the conversion of ssp-data
for i=1:L

    ssnew(i,:)=sspinter(c(i,:),range,rr)';
```

```

end
% This was the ordinary stuff. Now comes the meso data insertion:
% mesossp2 has the same range spacing as rr!!
R=input('Input range of most western point where mesodate is to be inserted (km): ');
ph=input('Input horizontal taper factor (fraction of range for each margin): ');pv=input('Input vertical taper
factor (fraction of total depth for bottom margin): ');
md=mean(mean(Dlyd)); %find mean value
DD=expfilt(Dlyd-md,ph,pv); %So much for tapering margins
fac=input('Input amplitude factor (0 - 1): ');
NVH=size(DD);
dzu=diff(zu);
zuu=(0:NVH(1)-1)*dzu(1); % new vertical range vector for the meso-data
% Now we need to interpolate the ssp-data vertically
for i=1:length(rr)
    cc(:,i)=tabinterp(-depth,ssnew(:,i),zuu);
end
% Include deepest part of the profile
nz=find(-depth>zuu(length(zuu)));
ccc=[cc;ssnew(nz,:)];
z=[zuu -depth(nz)];
% Be aware that also the bottom contains ssp-data now!
% Now ready to introduce mesossp-data
n=find(R<rr);
nD=size(DD);
if (length(n)>nD(2))
    n=n(1:nD(2)); %Use all of Dlyd
else
    nD(2)=length(n); %Use all of rr
end

ddd=ccc;% New result matrix
nz=length(zuu); %Number of depths in DD
for i=1:nz
    ddd(i,n)=ccc(i,n)+fac*DD(i,1:nD(2));
end
%finished with meso-data
%ready for output
outn=input('Navn pe resultatfil: ','s');
fo=fopen([outn 'm.ssp'],'w');
foo=fopen([outn 'o.ssp'],'w');

```

```
o=fopen([outn '.par'],'w');
st=-1;
for i=1:xii:KK
    fprintf(fo,'%d %f\n',st,rr(i));
    fprintf(foo,'%d %f\n',st,rr(i));

    for j=1:length(z)
        if (z(j)>=d(i)), break,end
        fprintf(fo,'%d %f\n',z(j),ddd(j,i));
        fprintf(foo,'%d %f\n',z(j),ccc(j,i));
    end
end
```

sspinter.m

```
function res=sspinter(origvektor,range,newrange)
% res=sspinter(origvektor,range,newrange)
% funksjon for interpolation in ssp data
% Assumes origvektor holds incomplete dataset with NaN also
% range is vector of ranges in origvektor
% answer in res with interpolated ranges in newrange (x3)
% result is in the same format as newrange!
% Modified from sspinterp 26/4-00
% H.H.
hh=size(origvektor);hhh=0;
c1=origvektor;
if (hh(1)>hh(2))
    ci=origvektor';hhh=1;
end
hh=size(range);
if (hh(1)>hh(2))
    range=range';
end
hh=size(range);
if (hh(1)>hh(2))
    range=range';
end

i0=min(find(c1>0));
i1=max(find(c1>0));
x2=range(i0:i1);
```

```

c2=c1(i0:i1);
x3=newrange;
if i0==i1
    res=origvektor(i0)*ones(size(x3));
else
    res=spline(x2,c2,x3);
end
res=res';

```

expfiltr.m

```

function z=expfiltr(y,ph,pv)
% function z=expfiltr(y,ph,pv)
% expands matrix y(n,m) by adding ph*m columns on each side,
% and pv*n rows below, such that the new parts taper towards zero
% i.e. the outer columns and rows of z are zero, except the first row.
% Last modified, H.H. 27/2-00.load mesossp.mat

```

```

[n,m]= size(y);
% vertical expansion first:
d=1/floor(n*pv);% number of rows to add -> coefficient
r=y(n,:); %master row
dr=(0:d:1-d);
ry=[y;rot90(r'*dr)];
% then horizontal expansion
[n,m]=size(ry);
d=1/floor(m*ph);
r1=ry(:,1); % left side master column
r2=ry(:,m); % right side master column
dr=(0:d:1-d);
z=[r1*dr, ry, fliplr(r2*dr)];

```

tabinter.m

```

function yi=tabinterp(x,y,xi)
% 1:D datainterpolasjon
% YI=tabinterp(X,Y,XI) returns vector YI containing elements
% corresponding to the elements of XI and determined by interpolation
% within vectors X and Y
% H.H. Last modified: 3/5-00
% convert to row vectors
[n,m]=size(x); if (n>m) x=x'; end

```

```
[n,m]=size(y); if (n>m) y=y'; end
[n,m]=size(xi); if (n>m) xi=xi'; end
dx=diff(x); dy=diff(y);
a=dy./dx; %coefficients
k0=length(xi);
    for k=1:k0
        ii=max(find(x<=xi(k)));
        yi(k)=y(ii)-a(ii)*(x(ii)-xi(k));
    end
```


a)

b)

Figure 7.3 (a) Sound speed distribution in the Fram Strait summer 70s. Original environmental data. (b) Sound speed distribution in the Fram Strait summer 70s. Meso data inserted at 300 km.

a)

b)

Figure 7.4 (a) Eigenrays for the case shown in Figure 7.3(a). (b) Eigenrays for the case shown in Figure 7.3(b).

Figure 7.5 Ray arrivals for factor=0.

Figure 7.6 Ray arrivals for factor=0.2.

Figure 7.7 Ray arrivals for factor=0.5.

Figure 7.8 Ray arrivals for factor=1.0.

Figure 7.9 Ray A variation with meso data.

Figure 7.10 Ray B variation with meso data.

Figure 7.11 Ray I variation with meso data.

Figure 7.12 Arrival time for the identified rays versus amplitude of meso data.

Figure 7.13 Ray fan results for Summer 50s.(a) Depth vs. source angle.(b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.14 Ray fan results for Winter 50s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.15 Ray fan results for summer 60s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.16 Ray fan results for Winter 60s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.17 Ray fan results for Summer 70s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.18 Ray fan results for Winter 70s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.19 Ray fan results for Summer 80s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.20 Ray fan results for Winter 80s. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.21 Ray fan results for Summer 50s. (a) Depth vs. receive angle. (b) Receive angle vs. source angle. (c) Arrival time vs. receive angle.

Figure 7.22 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with no range dependence - i.e. ssp as at the source. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.23 (a) Trace of rays belonging to region "ST". (b) Trace of rays of type a, A, g and h for all seasons.

Figure 7.24 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with meso-scale eddy at amplitude 0.2, 10% margins, insertion point 300 km. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.25 Ray fan results for Summer 60s, with meso-scale eddy at amplitude 1.0, 10% margins, insertion point 300 km. (a) Depth vs. source angle. (b) Arrival time vs. source angle. (c) Depth vs. arrival time.

Figure 7.26 Arrival time of eigenrays a, A, g, and h through seasons and decades. The winter seasons are shifted one year with respect to the summer seasons, and 109 s must be added to the ordinate.

8. Comparison of ray fans simulated with decadal mean environmental data and data from clima simulations under Task 2

The work presented in this chapter has been carried out by NERSC personnel.

The results from the simulations in Task 2 were unfortunately severely delayed, and became available only late in the fall 2000. The limited time remaining for the project has therefore prevented a thorough study of the influence of climatic predictions. Nevertheless, for the Fram Strait a few runs have been made with propagation of ray fan along a 200 km long trace along 79°N, starting 300 km from 18.7°W (corresponding to 137 km westwards from 11°W, the origin used in Chapter 7). The simulated climatic input data exist in form of monthly means for each year from 1950 to 2050. Spin up of the climatic model is from 1959 to 1980 - meaning that the results are unreliable until after 1980. Figure 8.1 show travel times of rays for a source at 500m depth and regardless of the depth at the receiver range, with simulations including CO₂. The features to be noticed is the change in the first arrival time of the ray groups, the mean travel time of the groups, and the spread in travel time. The mean travel time decreases slowly from 1960s on, with a rate about 6ms/year, but with local variations which are much higher. The control data (without CO₂) show almost the same features. From Figure 8.1 it is seen that in the period 1980-1990 the travel time of the first arrivals is very close to 136.0 s.

Figure 8.2 show results of similar runs using the mean environmental data sets as in Chapter 7, but with source and receiver located at the positions given above. The travel times for summers and winters are shifted slightly to enable them to be distinguished. The seasonal difference is marked, but was stronger in 1950s than in 1980s. The first arrivals are about 136.4 s in the summers of the last 3 decades. The correspondence in travel times between these two data sets is remarkable and comforting, and results not the least in a high degree of confidence in the climatic simulations.

It is not possible from Figure 8.2 to deduct any clear sign of warming of the water masses in the Fram Strait in the period 1950-1989. It should be observed, though, that the positioning of sound source and receiver is not optimal for sensing the West Spitsbergen current in these runs. Another matter is that if we use the mean measured environmental data sets and compute the mean temperature in the Fram Strait (including all water layers down to the bottom) we do not find any systematic change with time:

Table 8.1 Mean temperature in the Fram Strait, °C.

	Summer	Winter
50s	-0.252	-0.499
60s	-0.343	-0.498
70s	-0.382	-0.538
80s	-0.349	-0.490

8.1 Conclusions

- Comparison of ray travel times simulated with climatic models and measured mean environmental data show a very good correspondence.
- For the sound tracks used in this study the climatic simulations indicate an expected decrease in travel time of 6 ms/year.
- The measured environmental data for the period 1950-1989 show no systematic change in the mean water temperature in the Fram Strait.

Figure 8.1 Travel time from Task 2 climate simulations.

Figure 8.2 Travel time from environmental data.

9. Acknowledgement

We also acknowledge financial support from the Norwegian Research Council's Climate and Ozone Programme (project no. 121290/720), and the NATO Linkage Grant (E.NVIR.L G 960352)528 (96) LVdC.